

EURO BIOIMAGING

ANNUAL REPORT

2021

EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC

WE ARE THE EUROPEAN LANDMARK RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BIOLOGICAL AND BIOMEDICAL IMAGING AS RECOGNIZED BY THE EUROPEAN STRATEGY FORUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES (ESFRI). WE ARE THE GATEWAY TO NEARLY 150 WORLD-CLASS IMAGING FACILITIES ACROSS EUROPE.

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ABOUT US

FOREWORD FROM EURO-BIOIMAGING DIRECTORATE

JOHN ERIKSSON
Director General

ANTJE KEPPLER
Section Director Bio-Hub

LINDA CHAABANE
Section Director Med-Hub

In our second full year as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), we consolidated the strong foundations that took shape in 2019-2020 and continued to scale our infrastructure. Our family of Nodes grew significantly (8 new Nodes in 2021, i.e., a 30 percent increase), we welcomed one new member country, Poland, and the Euro-BioImaging technology offer continued to expand (50+ technologies). Our Nodes offered a range of training courses - online, hybrid, or even outdoors - and trained more researchers in cutting-edge imaging techniques and image analysis than ever before. Transnational user access was restrained by the pandemic, but innovations at our Nodes made virtual microscopy and remote experiments possible, so our Nodes continued to support excellent science despite the pandemic.

To boost user access, the Euro-BioImaging Hub team implemented two innovative funding mechanisms in 2021. The first mechanism, 85,000 euros, was funded by the Italian Ministry for Science and Research, to support Italian researchers travelling to Euro-BioImaging Nodes abroad and international researchers accessing Italian Euro-BioImaging Nodes with travel and access costs. This highly successful initiative led to twelve user projects in 2021. Overall, five applications for biological imaging technologies, five for biomedical in vivo imaging and two for ex-vivo imaging were supported. In addition, the

Euro-BioImaging Hub team set up a pilot user access fund of 50,000 euros to support user projects in October 2021. In total, 85 excellent proposals were received from 30 different countries around the world. In a highly competitive process, 10 of the most scientifically excellent, highly impactful proposals from the biomedical and biological imaging communities were selected for funding. France BioImaging funded an additional 9 user projects to their Node. The popularity of these initiatives clearly shows that there is a need to support researchers' access to cutting-edge imaging technologies financially.

At the Euro-BioImaging Hub team, we are fully aware of this outset. This is why we dedicated so much time and energy in 2021, alongside our partner life science research infrastructures and our Nodes, to responding to Horizon Europe calls and contributing to the European framework of the next years with a focus on infectious diseases, cancer, agroecology, and FAIR data sharing. In early 2022, we learned that our hard work on these proposals had paid off. By working together, we have secured close to 1.4M euros for transnational user projects with an imaging focus over the next 3-5 years. This, combined with funding initiatives, such as the Italian fund or the Pilot User Access fund, will translate to more transnational user projects in the coming years and facilitate excellent and impactful research.

INFRASTRUCTURE AT A GLANCE

Euro-BioImaging ERIC is the European Research Infrastructure for Biological and Biomedical Imaging, awarded the landmark status by ESFRI and thus recognized as the implemented reference infrastructure in the imaging field. Euro-BioImaging was established as an ERIC in the end of 2019.

The distributed Euro-BioImaging infrastructure builds on a set of already existing national and international centres of excellence in imaging technologies, the Euro-BioImaging Nodes, which provide physical or remote access to imaging technologies, deliver their training and support the users at all the stages of their research projects with their experienced staff.

Every researcher, both from academia and industry, can apply for Euro-BioImaging services whenever they have a project requiring imaging technologies and expertise but do not have the equipment or the skills to perform the experiments at their home institute.

The Nodes are jointly coordinated by the Euro-BioImaging Hub, which provides general supporting services including the management of user access, training coordination and services for image data.

Access to Euro-BioImaging services takes place through the Euro-BioImaging web portal at:

www.eurobioimaging.eu

KEY FIGURES 2021

17

MEMBERS
(COUNTRIES
& EMBL)

33

NODES

148

IMAGING
FACILITIES

31

BIOLOGICAL
IMAGING
TECHNOLOGIES

16

BIOMEDICAL
IMAGING
TECHNOLOGIES

101

USER
PROJECTS

3

COORDINATING
HUB SITES

DID YOU KNOW?

To optimally support the specific user needs in the biological and biomedical imaging communities, and at the same time ensure integration and overall coordination, the Euro-BioImaging Hub has a tripartite structure, in which Finland hosts the Statutory Seat, Italy hosts the Med-Hub, and EMBL hosts the Bio-Hub and Euro-BioImaging's general data services.

MAP OF EURO-BIOIMAGING MEMBERS & NODES

Cities where Euro-BioImaging facilities are located

Full members

Observers

Finland, EMBL & Italy host the three Hub sites

HIGHLIGHTS OF 2021

JAN FEB MAR APR MAY JUN JUL AUG SEP OCT NOV DEC

TECH EXCHANGE
1st Tech Exchange with Euro-BioImaging Industry Board

EOSC Future
EOSC Future project launched

€
Italian Fund to support Euro-BioImaging User Access launched

Poland becomes a member country

UNDERSTANDING CANCER
1st Euro-BioImaging User Forum

Horizon Europe announces funding for Infectious Disease research

INDUSTRY BOARD
Living Collaborations with Euro-BioImaging Industry Board

2nd Euro-BioImaging User Forum

BY-COVID
BY-COVID project kick-off

Euro-BioImaging joins EOSC Association

CORE SERVICES

USER ACCESS

Every researcher, both from academia and industry, can apply for Euro-Biolmaging services whenever they have a project requiring imaging technologies and expertise but do not have the equipment or skills to perform the experiments at their home Institute. Here's how it works:

INITIAL CONSULTATION

Potential users visit the Euro-Biolmaging web portal to select a technology and a Node, or contact Euro-Biolmaging directly to discuss their project and receive advice on technology and Node selection.

ACCESS REQUEST

After the technology and Node are selected, the user fills in the request form via the Euro-Biolmaging web portal: www.eurobioimaging.eu

SCIENTIFIC ADVICE

Applications receive scientific advice from external experts to support project development. In certain cases, no scientific check is necessary and the proposal can be fast-tracked to the technical check.

TECHNICAL ADVICE

The selected Node confirms the technical feasibility of the planned work. Once the access request is granted, the Node contacts the users regarding practicalities.

SERVICE PROVISION

A successful Euro-Biolmaging access request unlocks the power of imaging technologies and provides the expertise that users need to apply state-of-the-art imaging equipment to their project and analyze their results.

TECHNOLOGIES

Euro-Biolmaging offers open access to **50+ IMAGING TECHNOLOGIES** across scales, including the **9 NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN PROOF-OF-CONCEPT STUDY IN 2021** highlighted here:

ATOMIC FORCE MICROSCOPY (AFM)

Image credit: Pasi Kankaanpää

MASS SPECTROMETRY IMAGING (MSI)

Image credit: Italian Advanced Light Microscopy Node

MICRO X-RAY FLUORESCENCE SPECTROSCOPY (XRF)

Image credit: Reier, S., et al 2021. Used under Creative Commons license.

STRUCTURED ILLUMINATION MICROSCOPY (SIM)

Image credit: Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague CZ

COHERENT ANTI-STOKES RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY (CARS)

Image credit: Zdeněk Kostrouch

QUANTITATIVE PHASE IMAGING (QPI)

Image credit: Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague CZ

PHOTOACOUSTIC IMAGING (PAI)

Image credit: Capozza et al, 2018. Used under the CC BY-NC-ND license.

BIMODAL PHOTOACOUSTIC / OPTICAL COHERENCE TOMOGRAPHY (PAT/OCT)

Image credit: Austrian Biolmaging

MAGNETOENCEPHALOGRAPHY (MEG)

Image credit: Aalto Neuroimaging

DATA SERVICES

The cutting-edge imaging technologies offered by Euro-BioImaging are producing datasets of increasing volume, complexity, and information content. To realize the full potential of this ever growing resource and make image data Open and FAIR, Euro-BioImaging offers Image Data Services at its Nodes and the Hub.

Through the **Image Data Services at the Nodes**, our users can receive Image Analysis support both on the data acquired at the Node as well as stand alone analysis services on datasets acquired externally. Our image analysis experts at the Nodes can support user projects with, e.g., data handling, developing bespoke image analysis workflows, quantitative analysis, and access to analysis software.

Image Data Services at the Hub involve coordinating the analysis service provision at the Nodes, and representing the interests of the Imaging community in the European landscape by participating in **EOSC** (European Open Science Cloud) projects,

such as EOSC-Life and EOSC Future. The Hub works towards alignment of the numerous international image data and metadata initiatives, while shaping future developments of European Open Science policy through our membership in the EOSC Association and its Task Forces. To drive image data FAIRification, the Euro-BioImaging Hub contributes to the development of technical solutions that benefit the whole imaging community, such as next generation file formats, while developing metadata guidelines and supporting image data repositories like the **BioImage Archive**. With our data services at the Nodes and the Hub, we provide crucial support to the European and global image data community.

EMPOWERING THE IMAGING COMMUNITY WITH OPEN AND FAIR IMAGE DATA & ANALYSIS SERVICES

TRAINING

With the advances in imaging technology, more and more new technologies are available to users, making training in the correct use of the technologies and the connected sample preparation and data analysis crucial. The Euro-BioImaging Nodes offer a wide range of training opportunities.

The Training offer covers the **full spectrum of technologies** available from biological to biomedical imaging, as well as many courses focusing on **sample preparation** and handling and **image data analysis**. Some courses are taught remotely and virtually, increasing their accessibility. For more details on **remote trainings** provided by our Nodes, see p. 52-53.

THE TRAINING COURSES AT EURO-BIOIMAGING NODES

- are available for users, students and facility staff,
- combine theory and hands-on learning,
- are taught in English,
- are open for anyone to apply to.

190+
NUMBER OF TRAINING COURSES OFFERED

29
NUMBER OF NODES OFFERING TRAINING COURSES

A LIST OF THE UPCOMING TRAINING COURSES IS AVAILABLE AT

www.eurobioimaging.eu/content/training

The word cloud represents the topics covered by training courses offered by Euro-BioImaging Nodes.

OUR TEAM

Euro-BioImaging ERIC is coordinated by the Hub Team. The Euro-BioImaging Hub consists of a **Statutory Seat** in Finland (Turku), a community-specific **Bio-Hub** for biological imaging at EMBL (Heidelberg), and a

community-specific **Med-Hub** for biomedical imaging in Italy (Torino). In 2021, our Hub team expanded to include an Image Data Coordinator, a Web Portal Developer, and a Quality Management team.

EURO-BIOIMAGING HUB TEAM IN 2022

JOHN ERIKSSON
Director General
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

ANTJE KEPPLER
Section Director
Bio-Hub
Euro-BioImaging
Bio-Hub | EMBL

LINDA CHAABANE
Section Director
Med-Hub
Euro-BioImaging
Med-Hub | Torino

JOHANNA BISCHOF
Scientific
Project Manager
Euro-BioImaging
Bio-Hub | EMBL

MARIANNA CHILDRESS-POLI
External
Communication
Officer
Euro-BioImaging
Bio-Hub | EMBL

GIUSEPPE DIGILIO
Operations Advisor
Euro-BioImaging
Med-Hub | Torino

SOLVEIG ERIKSSON
Multimedia
Producer
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

CAMILO GUZMÁN
Scientific Officer -
Quality Management
of Biological Imaging
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

MILAD KAKOULI
Software
Developer
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

PASI KANKAANPÄÄ
Senior
Scientific Manager
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

HENOK KARVONEN
Multimedia
Producer
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

DARIO LONGO
Scientific
Project Manager
Euro-BioImaging
Med-Hub | Torino

RAKESH MAHATO
Software
Developer
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

AASTHA MATHUR
Image Data
Services
Coordinator
Euro-BioImaging
Bio-Hub | EMBL

BUĞRA ÖZDEMİR
Image Data
Specialist
Euro-BioImaging
Bio-Hub | EMBL

CLAUDIA PFANDER
Industry Board
Coordinator
Euro-BioImaging
Bio-Hub | EMBL

ILARI PULLI
Organization
Coordinator
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

ARINA RYBINA
Scientific
Project Manager
Euro-BioImaging
Bio-Hub | EMBL

SUSANNE VAINIO
Scientific Officer -
Quality Management
of Medical Imaging
Euro-BioImaging
Statutory Seat | Turku

ALESSANDRA VIALE
Scientific
Project Manager
Euro-BioImaging
Med-Hub | Torino

MANY THANKS!

In 2021, several of our team members moved on to new horizons. We want to thank them for their contributions and wish them much success in their new professional endeavors!

Professor Silvio Aime can be considered a pioneer in the field of diagnostic imaging agents and was a key player in building the Euro-Biolmaging ERIC from the ground up. From 2008-2013, he chaired the “Molecular Imaging” Work Package in the Preparatory Phase of the ESFRI Large Scale Facility (EU-LSF) “Euro-Biolmaging” and was the Italian delegate of the preparatory organization from 2013 until ERIC status was granted in 2019. Thanks to his vocation to build the imaging community, he brought together several excellent facilities from the biomedical and medical field to form the Italian Multi-sited Multi-Modal Molecular Imaging (MMMI) Node. He also oversaw the creation of the Phase Contrast Imaging Flagship Node Trieste.

In 2019, he accepted to act as Interim Director of the Euro-Biolmaging Med-Hub, in addition to his institutional and scientific commitments at the University of Torino.

Looking back on his experience, Professor Aime is proud of the way Euro-Biolmaging has evolved, becoming a European research infrastructure that combines advanced imaging technologies and expertise in the field with a commitment to support the scientific community.

We want to thank Professor Aime for his fundamental contributions to the Euro-Biolmaging ERIC. Under his lead as Interim Director of the Med-Hub, the number of Medical Imaging Nodes doubled and three Mixed Nodes joined our Euro-Biolmaging family. In addition, our medical imaging portfolio expanded to include 16 biomedical imaging technologies, including three technologies that were new to our portfolio. Finally, the Italian User Access Fund supported by the Italian Ministry for Education & Research was introduced and implemented under Professor Aime’s leadership.

Professor Aime’s commitment to bringing the biological and biomedical imaging communities together, his vast knowledge and expertise, his recognition by the global biomedical imaging community and his generosity in mobilizing his personal connections to benefit Euro-Biolmaging has greatly contributed to building our research infrastructure.

We are extremely thankful for all he has done to ensure our fledgling infrastructure is able to take flight. We sincerely hope he will remain part of the Euro-Biolmaging community in the years to come.

“‘Mixed’ Nodes bring together skills and competences from both the biological and biomedical imaging communities in one Node. The two communities are coming together for the benefit of life science research - and it is something to be proud of.”

- Silvio Aime

2019-2021 LEGACY

2x

INCREASE IN MED-NODES

16

BIOMEDICAL IMAGING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EURO-BIOIMAGING PORTFOLIO

12

USER PROJECTS SUPPORTED BY THE ITALIAN USER ACCESS FUND

OTHER TEAM MEMBERS

We also want to thank the other colleagues who have moved on for their contributions to our infrastructure. **Frauke Leitner** joined the Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub during the Preparatory Phase. She managed the CORBEL project, which supported cross-research infrastructure user access, and represented Euro-Biolmaging within EOSC-Life as WP3 co-lead. **Federica Paina** joined Euro-Biolmaging Bio-

Hub during the Preparatory Phase. She represented and advised Euro-Biolmaging on policy issues and external relations. She was also instrumental in building the Global Biolmaging network. **Sara Zullino** was part of the Euro-Biolmaging Med-Hub. She made a very important contribution to the biomedical imaging data management community within EOSC-Life Demonstrator 5.

ACHIEVEMENTS 2021

MESSAGE FROM PREPATORY PHASE COORDINATOR

This is a time of unprecedented opportunity and need for life science. For the first time we can directly see the molecular mechanisms that drive living systems and obtain critical knowledge to predict how life will function in a changing world. To use this opportunity, the life science community must democratize access to the most advanced imaging technologies that power our research. Euro-BiolImaging's establishment as an ERIC has been a key step towards this goal.

During the Euro-BiolImaging preparation period from 2010-2019, which I coordinated, I would say that together we built four strong pillars to carry the future Euro-BiolImaging house. (i) A reputation of service excellence in the user community; (ii) a model for joint governance by different life science communities; (iii) trust between the member state governments and the scientists organizing the RI; and (iv) strong links with our RI partners in Europe and around the world.

In its 2nd annual report, the young ERIC looks back at a turbulent start as an independent RI. Celebrating its brand-new statutes at the end of 2019 meant being hit immediately by the COVID-19 lockdowns. Born into challenging times, Euro-BiolImaging proved its value, providing virtual collaboration forums, a portfolio of remote services, and support for COVID-19 research. Emerging from this "baptism by fire", Euro-BiolImaging has built an amazing Hub team, added new Nodes, and renewed its support from over ten EC calls that will power user access and new data services.

In a way, Euro-BiolImaging is just starting now, as pandemic management - a triumph of life sciences! - allows user access to resume. Now is the time to reinforce it for full operation and enable as much groundbreaking life science as possible. Winning ten EC grants is a great success, yet managing and delivering them is a major task and working closely with the EC on sustaining transnational user access a key mission for the future. The visibility of Euro-BiolImaging in user communities from disciplines other than biology and medicine needs promotion

JAN ELLENBERG

Head of the Cell Biology & Biophysics Unit and the EMBL Imaging Centre

and its technology portfolio has to stay abreast with disruptive developments. Euro-BiolImaging takes these tasks on proactively, has already upgraded some of its Nodes (including EMBL's new Imaging Centre) and has placed new bids with the EC to participate in technology development, so it can pick them up for service right away.

After many years of preparation, it is a real joy for me to see Euro-BiolImaging getting going on the ground. Euro-BiolImaging connects scientists across countries and cultures, that are united by seeking new knowledge and using the best imaging technology for this universal human endeavor. Especially in current times, it is so rewarding to see the spirit of international collaboration spread. Ultimately, this has been our motivation, even in the most difficult moments of the preparatory phase, and it will make the Euro-BiolImaging community larger and stronger. Just take a look at what's already possible now. Hundreds of scientists access the best imaging technologies every year. Enabled by Euro-BiolImaging, they will make extraordinary discoveries that increase our understanding of life and improve the well-being and resilience of our societies.

STRATEGIC PLAN

2019-2023

Euro-Biolmaging's 1st Strategic Plan was approved at the first meeting of the Euro-Biolmaging Board in December 2019. It presents the Euro-Biolmaging ERIC activities and tasks as approved and funded by its launching members, comprising the period from Euro-Biolmaging ERIC launch in 2019, until the research infrastructure concludes its first operational cycle in 2023. The key goal during these first five years is to make Euro-Biolmaging ERIC the internationally

recognized reference research infrastructure in Europe that serves all scientists with imaging needs.

The strategy includes establishing the Euro-Biolmaging ERIC as its own legal entity, launching and scaling its operational services, establishing the ERIC governance as well as the Euro-Biolmaging Hub and Nodes as functional entities for opening their services to the communities.

As of 2021, we are pleased to report that our infrastructure is on track with its strategic objectives. After kick-starting our operations in 2020, here are the key achievements of 2021:

- ✓ Supported a 30 percent increase in our community of Nodes
- ✓ Added new technologies to our technology portfolio
- ✓ Received 2.5 times more user proposals than in 2020
- ✓ Finalized Service Level Agreements with new Nodes
- ✓ Expanded the Hub team to include an Image Data Services Coordinator, new Euro-Biolmaging Web Portal developer, and two Quality Managers
- ✓ Increased ERIC membership (Poland joined)
- ✓ Finalized our Governance by electing the Panel of Node Chairs
- ✓ Finalized the recruitment of the Director General and the Bio-Hub Director
- ✓ Launched two unique opportunities to fund Euro-Biolmaging User Access
- ✓ Strengthened our position with regards to FAIR image data sharing & services in the context of other European Research Infrastructures
- ✓ Secured 1.4M euros funding via Horizon Europe projects to support transnational user access to Euro-Biolmaging Nodes

STATUS AS OF 2021

In 2021, we successfully continued operations of the first pan-European research infrastructure for imaging technologies, showing the world that Euro-Biolmaging ERIC is open and ready for business.

To support our operations and growth, we continued to look for external funding sources to supplement member contributions, and

were amazed by the breathtaking rate at which our infrastructure continued to expand.

On the opposite page is a timeline to illustrate the operational implementation of our infrastructure since 2019 as well as its impressive evolution. Currently we are in preparation for the first evaluation phase which will start in 2022.

IMPLEMENTATION

Euro-Biolmaging implementation of governance and operational services such as user access, web portal, has been completed.

SCALABILITY

Our infrastructure has continued to expand since 2019, with regards to our family of Nodes, our technology offer, our user community and our Hub Team.

EVALUATION

The evaluation phase of Euro-Biolmaging begins in 2022 in close coordination with the Scientific Advisory Board.

FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES

FIRST OPEN CALL FOR EURO-BIOIMAGING USER ACCESS

In October 2021, Euro-BioImaging launched the Pilot User Access Fund with a call for user projects to receive funding support. This Fund provides financial support of up to 5,000 euros for researchers to take advantage of the imaging services provided by the 33 Euro-BioImaging Nodes.

In total, 85 applications were submitted for the Euro-BioImaging Access Fund, a sign of the overwhelming popularity of this funding opportunity in our community.

The received applications covered a very wide range of different imaging technologies in the Euro-BioImaging portfolio. Access and support from 25 out of the 33 Euro-BioImaging Nodes was requested in the received proposals. The range of research topics in the applications was also very broad, from plant biology to topics with an impact on human health, like oncology, drug discovery, neuroscience, immunology and virology.

FIRST OPEN CALL AT A GLANCE

- 50,000€** For biological & biomedical imaging projects
- 85** Applications received
- 30** Different countries
- 75%** Requests for transnational access
- 10** Successful proposals

FOR MORE INFORMATION:

The successful projects were selected in a two-stage process, including first a review by our standing board of expert scientific reviewers and secondly a review and selection by a panel of selected scientific experts. Through this process 10 proposals from the biomedical and biological imaging communities were selected for funding. Successful proposals were judged to be scientifically excellent, highly impactful and likely to advance knowledge in the field. Special attention was given to proposals that involved transnational access.

Euro-BioImaging is proud of the outstanding level of interest in this pilot Call for funded User projects, demonstrating the broad range of excellent science supported by imaging and the impact of our infrastructure.

MAP OF USER PROPOSAL COUNTRIES (FOCUS ON EUROPE)

85 applications were received from users in more than 30 countries, with a zoom in on European countries above. The color scale refers to the number of applications received from each country.

THE ITALIAN USER ACCESS GRANTS PROGRAM

In 2021, the Italian Ministry of Universities and Research kindly provided a 85,000 euro fund to support transnational user access to and from Italy. The Italian User Access Grants Program was launched in March and supports Italian researchers travelling to Euro-BioImaging Nodes abroad and international researchers accessing Italian Euro-BioImaging Nodes with their travel and access costs. Grants were assigned on a first come, first served basis.

User Projects covered a wide range of applications, from biology to preclinical and ex-vivo studies. Overall, five applications for biological imaging technologies, five for biomedical in vivo imaging and two for ex-vivo imaging were received.

We would like to thank the Italian Ministry of University and Research for this initiative, which was very successful in promoting the Italian Nodes and stimulating transnational user access, in spite of the mobility restrictions due to COVID-19 pandemic. We are also convinced that users who visited our Nodes thanks to this fund will contribute to spread the word about the quality and usefulness of Euro-BioImaging services within the international scientific community.

ITALIAN FUND AT A GLANCE

- 85,000€** For biological & biomedical imaging projects
- 2,500€/PROJECT** For Italian researchers
- 7,500€/PROJECT** For international researchers visiting Italian Nodes
- 12** User projects selected in 2021
- 4** Italian Nodes selected by users

FUNDED BY THE ITALIAN MINISTRY OF UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH

SUPPORTING USER PROJECTS

At Euro-Biolmaging, our key mission is to provide access, services and training to state-of-the-art imaging technologies for all life scientists in Europe and beyond. 2020-2021 were challenging years due to the pandemic travel restrictions, but in 2021, the number of user projects more than doubled. These numbers were boosted by the funding mechanisms that we put in place with the support of our members, including the Italian User Access Fund and the Pilot User Access Call. A total of 21 user projects from proposals received in the Pilot User Access Call in 2021 will take place in 2022. We look forward to exciting scientific results.

 186 PROPOSALS	
 35 DIFFERENT TECHNOLOGIES REQUESTED	

* Excluding Pilot User Access Call proposals

OUR TOP 3 IMAGING TECHNOLOGIES IN 2021

The Euro-Biolmaging technology portfolio is vast. Composed of **50+ imaging technologies**, here is a selection of the most requested technologies by users for biological and biomedical imaging projects.

BIOMEDICAL IMAGING

1. High Field MRI
2. PET/CT
3. In vivo Optical Imaging

BIOLOGICAL IMAGING

1. Laser scanning confocal microscopy (LSCM)
2. Electron Microscopy (EM)
3. Stimulated emission depletion microscopy (STED)

Beate Neumann of the EMBL ALMF supports user Chiara Cassioli with a high throughput RNAi screening project. Copyright: EMBL/PhotoLab Massimo Del Prete

USER STORIES

“Competent, professional, and collaborative staff at the ALEMBIC Node in Milan! I received excellent support for my project: from the sample preparation for electron microscopy to the acquisition and analysis of the data.”

- Arcangela Iuso, Institute of Neurogenomics, HMGU, visiting the ALEMBIC Facility in Milan, part of the Italian ALM Node

“Even before I arrived at EMBL, the ALMF team had been extremely supportive of our project, advising us at each step of the development of a customer-based RNAi assay, helping us to choose the best cell line and read-out to address our biological question, and helping us to improve our sample preparation to acquire good quality images for co-localization analysis.”

Copyright: EMBL/PhotoLab Massimo Del Prete

- Chiara Cassioli, University of Sienna, visiting the EMBL Node

“Being able to travel and work in the ALEMBIC facility as a Euro-Biolmaging user alongside other experts has been an extremely rich experience. Combining correlative electron microscopy and three-dimensional (3D) tomographic volumes, we were able to decipher the pathogenic signals that lead to accumulation of dysfunctional and/or damaged mitochondria in patient-derived cells with methylmalonic acidemia (MMA)– a life-threatening disorder that often manifest in childhood and with no curative, first-line treatment option available to date. Some earlier results of this ongoing collaboration have been published in Nature Communications (Luciani et al. Nature Communications 11: 970, 2020).”

- Alessandro Luciani, University of Zurich, visiting the ALEMBIC Facility in Milan, part of the Italian ALM Node

“Bone fracture comprehension is still limited to macro- and meso-scale level, where its occurrence is catastrophic. It is still unclear what befalls at the micro-scale from a mechanobiological point of view and what is the role of microscopic bone porosities, named lacunae, during the damage processes. To shed some light on this complexity, synchrotron imaging at Euro-Biolmaging Phase Contrast Imaging Flagship Node in Trieste is an essential step forward: indeed, the phase contrast allows us to detect micro-crack initiation and progression with an unprecedented resolution. Additionally, the combination of imaging and micro-mechanical tests offers the possibility to perform quantitative observations on stress intensification sites in human bones.”

- Drs. Federica Buccino, Laura Vergani & Sara Bagherifard, Politecnico di Milano, visiting the Phase Contrast Imaging Flagship Node, Trieste

ADVANCING OPEN SCIENCE

SHAPING THE FUTURE OF OPEN SCIENCE

Publishing data from facilities and linking FAIR databases to open and reusable tools and workflows to make imaging data accessible and reusable is part of Euro-Biolmaging’s mission. To support this mission, EMBL hosts the Euro-Biolmaging image data services and the open image data repository, BioImage Archive.

Since March 2019, Euro-Biolmaging is a strong partner in the EOSC-Life project, working with the imaging communities and 12 other ESFRI research infrastructures to ensure that life sciences have their space in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). As of April 2021, Euro-Biolmaging also participates in EOSC Future,

EOSC ASSOCIATION TASK FORCE

The EOSC Association plays an important role in coordinating investments in the Open Science Cloud via its Task Forces and other governance structures. To further steer the future of data science, Euro-Biolmaging representatives were selected to be involved in two of the EOSC Association Task Forces, addressing key areas of implementation.

demonstrating concrete examples of implementation of the EOSC in life science research via one of their Test Science Projects. In order to better contribute to the future of EOSC, Euro-Biolmaging decided to join the EOSC Association in 2021 as a full member, joining forces with over 230 other members and observers, including partner ESFRI research infrastructures.

Joining the EOSC Association is a logical step for our data-heavy infrastructure, because this will allow us to help guide the strategy for coordinating investment and shaping the future of Open Science on a European level.

THESE TASK FORCES ARE:

- RESEARCHER ENGAGEMENT & ADOPTION
- TECHNICAL INTEROPERABILITY

“ We are glad to be selected to represent interests of the imaging community in future EOSC endeavors. We aim to bring our users’ needs to the EOSC, while priming them towards ownership and adoption of EOSC services. Technical interoperability opens doors towards potential cross-domain interactions.

- Aastha Mathur, Image Data Coordinator at Euro-Biolmaging and member of the EOSC Association Task Force

MISSION

Euro-Biolmaging’s key mission is to enable European researchers, both from academia and industry, to benefit from innovative biological and biomedical imaging technologies, expertise, data services and training essential for performing cutting-edge research. These services are available to every researcher who applies via our portal. In addition, Euro-Biolmaging ERIC has a crucial role to play as an ESFRI Landmark, contributing to the overall competitiveness of the European Research Area.

CONTRIBUTING TO THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

EXCELLENCE

- ✓ Attracts users to conduct cutting-edge imaging research
- ✓ Attracts and retains talent at its Hub and Nodes
- ✓ Supports training offer delivered by best experts in the field
- ✓ Supports Open Data and EOSC within the transition to Open Science

INTERNATIONAL ENGAGEMENT

- ✓ Supports tackling the Grand Societal Challenges and international commitments as set out in UN Sustainable Development Goals with Global BioImaging partners
- ✓ Increases visibility of Nodes and European science at international level
- ✓ Attracts international user access

SOCIETAL & ECONOMIC IMPACT

- ✓ Responds to key societal challenges (e.g., COVID)
- ✓ Works closely with EU research infrastructures on EU missions: cancer, healthy soil and climate change
- ✓ Works closely with Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board
- ✓ Shares user success stories and disseminates science to society

INTEGRATION

- ✓ 17 ERIC members across all European regions
- ✓ 33 national Nodes with 148 individual facilities hosted by its ERIC members
- ✓ Transparent procedure with independent evaluation to include new national Nodes

FUNDED PROJECTS

EOSC-LIFE

Ensuring that European Life Science research remains innovative and efficient in developing integratable solutions requires that digital resources such as research data, services and platforms are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) - regardless of scientific discipline and national boundary.

In EOSC-Life, Euro-Biolmaging works towards that goal - with the 12 other Life Science Research Infrastructures - by building an open, digital and collaborative space for biological and medical research in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This will allow European researchers to directly address key societal challenges and drive the bio-economy.

54

MONTHS
MAR 2019 - AUG 2023

46

PARTNERS

13

TOTAL WORK
PACKAGES

26

MILLION
EUROS

GOALS OF EOSC-LIFE

- Establish EOSC-Life by publishing FAIR life science data resources in EOSC
- Provide the policies, guidelines and processes for secure and ethical data reuse
- Populate an ecosystem of innovative life-science tools in EOSC
- Enable data-driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to EOSC via open calls for participation
- Provide training to scientific communities

DID YOU KNOW

Euro-Biolmaging co-leads EOSC-Life Work Package 2 on Tools & Workflows and Work Package 3, which is responsible for Demonstrator projects & Open Calls for User Projects. We also contribute to activities in a number of other work packages, such as training, dissemination and international engagement.

CLOUD-BASED IMAGE ANALYSIS TOOLS, WORKFLOWS AND WORKSPACES

Image analysis is central in modern bio-imaging, but cloud-based image analysis is still not commonly used. To develop tools for the imaging community, Euro-Biolmaging works in EOSC-Life WP2 to drive the deployment of image analysis tools on remote computational resources and make them accessible for the community.

GALAXY FOR IMAGING

Euro-Biolmaging is developing and promoting the use of the Galaxy workflow management platform for bioimage analysis by making image analysis tools and workflows available on the platform and improving Galaxy support for image data types.

Because Galaxy is widely used in many life sciences communities and beyond, its use for image analysis ensures interoperability with tools from other domains. The use of a workflow management system also contributes to the FAIRification of bioimage analysis workflows which can be deposited in the WorkflowHub.

<https://imaging.usegalaxy.eu>

www.lifemonitor.eu

www.workflowhub.eu

FAIR TOOLS AND WORKFLOWS IN THE EOSC

Within EOSC-Life, Euro-Biolmaging and partner Research Infrastructure Instruct ERIC co-lead Work Package 2, whose objective is to facilitate the porting of scientific workflows produced in the framework of the RIs to the EOSC environment and help make them FAIR.

CLOUD-BASED WORKFLOWS

Among numerous activities, WP2 has developed WorkflowHub as an inclusive workflow registry, agnostic to any Workflow Management System, which allows researchers to search over and launch workflows directly from WorkflowHub in Galaxy. To allow computational workflows to remain reusable and useful to the community over time, they need to undergo periodic testing to establish that all components and tools for the workflow are still functional. To do this, EOSC-Life WP2 has developed the LifeMonitor service, which was first released in May 2021.

A VIRTUAL DESKTOP FOR BIOIMAGE ANALYSIS

Recognizing that bioimage analysis often involves extensive human interventions with the use of multiple graphical tools, WP2 has developed the Bioimage ANalysis Desktop (BAND, <https://band.embl.de>), a Desktop-as-a-Service platform that offers a configurable desktop environment within the user's web browser and is accessible to everyone in the imaging community.

The BAND desktops are populated with widely-used image analysis tools and include support for GPUs and remote data access via Nextcloud/ownCloud, XNAT and S3-compatible object storage. The Virtual Desktop BAND has already been successfully used in e.g. two Bio-IT deep learning courses and has more than 150 registered users.

DEMONSTRATOR PROJECT #6

An example Galaxy workflow using Cell-Profiler and public image data was developed in WP3 as EOSC-Life demonstrator project #6. This workflow showcases in particular a tool to stage images from the IDR or any OMERO database directly onto a Galaxy server. This work highlights how the developed tools can be used to gather new insights from previously run experiments to conduct resource-efficient research. A tutorial is available on <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>, (there select Imaging/Nucleoli segmentation and feature extraction using CellProfiler), so you can try out the workflow and see how it can be applied to your data.

“Imagine a dynamic Digital Network for Research: effectively inter-connecting access to high-quality Data, Analysis Tools, Cloud Resources and a wide spectrum of Life Sciences expertise - Open for all scientists! EOSC-Life is bringing this Vision to Reality across Research Infrastructures! And contributing to this fantastic goal and community is highly inspiring.

- Arina Rybina, Scientific Project Manager at Euro-Biolmaging and EOSC-Life Project Manager

CALLS FOR PILOT PROJECTS

One of the key goals of EOSC-Life is to connect the large European life science research community with the EOSC. To achieve this goal, Work Package 3, led by Euro-BioImaging and Instruct, has run three calls for pilot projects. Following the highly successful first call in 2020, 2021 saw the launch of two additional calls for projects dealing with sensitive data, and projects involving academia-industry collaboration.

These calls offered expert support and consultation to the applicants to develop their project idea during the application process via the maturation phase. Successful applicants receive funding as well as support from EOSC-Life experts and training opportunities.

Overall, 11 projects were selected via the highly competitive WP3 calls and evaluation process, covering a very wide range of topics and arising from different RI domains. With support by WP3, the project teams are integrated into the EOSC-Life community via regular meetings, expert consultations and training events, such as the EOSC-Life FAIR Hackathon.

FUNDED PROJECTS INCLUDE:

- Integrating EU-RI datasets for preclinical and discovery research bioimaging
- Towards FAIR data for X-ray-based structure-guided drug design
- Open Source Secure Data Infrastructure and Processes for Life Sciences (OSSDIP4LIFE)
- QSM4SENIOR: Ultra-high Field MRI Quantitative Susceptibility Mapping reconstruction of the healthy Brain-aging cohort

READ MORE

You can find details of all funded projects at www.eosc-life.eu/calls/ and relevant outcomes for the imaging community will be reported in future annual reports.

EOSC FUTURE

EOSC Future is an EU-funded H2020 project that builds on the existing baseline for the European Open Science Cloud to deliver a platform with a durable set of user-friendly components that are designed for the long haul. This project adopts a system-of-systems approach to the platform, linking together other research portals, resources and services to respond to the data needs of a wide range of researchers.

Within EOSC Future, Euro-BioImaging works together with partner RIs EU-Openscreen ERIC and Instruct ERIC to implement an EOSC Future Test Science Project on “Open Imaging Data Sharing in EOSC: COVID-19 as Demonstrator”. The proposed work includes facilitating rapid sharing of Covid-19 related High-throughput microscopy data through a modular, shareable, open, and FAIR workflow.

The demonstrator project targets developments with Galaxy for submitting data to the BioImage Archive and involved close collaboration with the OME team on data formats. The work accomplished in EOSC Future will greatly facilitate integration and sharing of large-scale FAIR image data sets via EOSC across disciplines within the life sciences and beyond, thereby enabling and stimulating collaborative image-based science.

www.eoscfuture.eu

BY-COVID

BY-COVID will tackle the data challenges that can hinder effective pandemic responses. The core aim of the project is to ensure that data on SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious diseases can be found and used by everyone as soon as they are available. BY-COVID will build and expand upon the successful COVID-19 Data Platform, a resource initiated in the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic and led by EMBL-EBI.

Within this project, Euro-BioImaging co-leads WP2, “Accessing heterogeneous data across domains and jurisdictions for enabling the downstream processing of COVID-19 and future pandemic episodes data.” Our role is to ensure valuable imaging datasets are available for reuse in public repositories like BioImage Archive & COVID19 Data Portal to bolster research & support pandemic readiness.

BY-COVID is a Horizon Europe funded project, launched in October 2021, and will build on the One-Health approach, exploit and contribute to the European Open Science Cloud and work closely with the ISIDORE project.

<https://by-covid.org/>

HEALTHY CLOUD

The HealthyCloud project gathers 5 European Research Infrastructures and 3 Joint Actions, each with its own particularities about health data generation, acquisition and management. The aim of the project is to generate guidelines, recommendations and specifications that will enable distributed health research across Europe in the form of a Ready-to-implement Roadmap. This will be the basis to produce the final HealthyCloud Strategic Agenda for the implementation of the European Health Research and Innovation Cloud (HRIC). Within the HealthyCloud project, Euro-BioImaging will contribute to the health data landscape analysis, with a focus on imaging data, in sharing the expertise in medical image data

management with the XNAT platform and in the analysis of existing data hubs' governance. It will provide metadata models for imaging datasets and contribute to two use cases by providing diagnostic images associated with biological samples and clinical data from oncological and cardiological patients.

ISIDORE

To foster Europe's responsiveness to pandemic-prone pathogens, as well as resilience against major infectious-disease threats, the European Union funds, via the Horizon Europe Emergency call framework, a consortium called **I**ntegrated **S**ervices for **I**nfectious **D**isease **O**utbreak **R**esearch (ISIDORE).

The project provides access to key services to effectively support and implement studies on pathogens including SARS-CoV-2 and its variants. Euro-BioImaging co-leads together with partner RI Instruct the work package dedicated to the "Provision of Access to analytical services". Via this work package, researchers will be able to receive funded access to cutting-edge imaging technologies to address their infectious disease research questions at 19 Euro-BioImaging Nodes. In ISIDORE, Euro-BioImaging also contributes to scientific coordination, FAIR data handling, quality management, training and outreach.

ISIDORE unites a multidisciplinary consortium of 17 European research infrastructures with the aim of harnessing and integrating the research infrastructure services to combat current and future infectious disease outbreaks. It is coordinated by our partner Research Infrastructure ERINHA and brings together more than 150 service providers from 32 countries and a total funding of 21 million euros. ISIDORE is a project of unprecedented dimensions in the European Research Area and serves as a central instrument in the European R&D response to epidemic outbreaks, as well as aligning with global strategies for pandemic management and preparedness.

PROJECT PERSPECTIVES

TOWARDS MORE TRANSNATIONAL USER ACCESS FUNDING

Transnational user access - the ability for researchers to access the best and most suitable imaging technologies wherever they are available, even in a different country - has been fundamental to Euro-BioImaging since the very beginning.

HORIZON EUROPE FUNDING TO SUPPORT TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS

The funded projects that Euro-BioImaging is a partner in, which include opportunities for transnational access driving traffic to Euro-BioImaging Nodes, are:

The outstanding number of applications for the Euro-BioImaging Pilot User Access Fund, launched in October 2021 (for more details, see p. 22) highlight that when funding is available, a much broader segment of researchers is able to consider how cutting-edge imaging technologies could improve their research. Indeed, lack of funding for user access is a bottleneck in the full utilisation of open access imaging technologies to benefit all research areas and address societal challenges.

CANSERV - In this project, Euro-BioImaging will offer a large portfolio of imaging services in basic research, drug discovery, early development, as well as access to population image data and image analysis services dedicated to cancer research.

AGROSERV - In this consortium, Euro-BioImaging will offer imaging services to researchers through a selection of Nodes targeting topics of agroecology, plant biology, water, soil, and microorganisms.

As Euro-BioImaging does not currently have continuous funding to support user access, in 2021 the Euro-BioImaging Hub was very active in preparing applications within the Horizon Europe program framework the European Commission, to secure funding for user access to the Euro-BioImaging Nodes.

Other projects that received funding in which Euro-BioImaging plays key roles are **Ai4LIFE**, where Euro-BioImaging, as the coordinating Research Infrastructure, will develop cutting-edge AI services for image analysis. **EOSC4Cancer**, focused on FAIR and open data sharing in support of cancer research and **eRImote**, are projects where we will contribute to the transition to digital/remote research infrastructure service provision.

Euro-BioImaging has been immensely successful, as 100 percent of the Horizon Europe grant proposals we worked on with our Nodes and our partner research infrastructures in 2021 will be funded. This shows the strength of our infrastructure and the importance of imaging services in driving excellent science and solving a variety of global societal challenges. The newly funded projects will launch in 2022 and facilitate transnational access to our Nodes in support of outstanding science between 2022-2025!

Euro-BioImaging looks forward to working on this array of projects with partner research infrastructures and our Nodes and seeing the expanded access to imaging infrastructures for all researchers resulting from the projects.

EXCELLENT SCIENCE

ESSAY BY DIRECTOR GENERAL

SEEING THE VISIBLE AND THE INVISIBLE WORLD WITH NEW EYES

Euro-Bioimaging became an ERIC in late 2019 but had to go in stealth mode soon after. In March 2020, Europe was closed for business – just as our fledgling infrastructure was entering its first year of operations. But we made the most of the unprecedented situation, building our community up online and supporting Nodes & users in the mostly uncharted terrain of virtual microscopy and remote training.

In 2021, while the pandemic still affected daily operations, we had the first concrete views of the Horizon Europe landscape and how it will leverage research infrastructures to support excellent science across Europe. First calls opened almost right away and half a year was spent on Zoom meetings while grants for a broad spectrum of proposals were prepared and written related to infectious diseases, cancer, agroecology, artificial intelligence, data handling, and remote access. In early 2022, we learned that all proposals we had worked on were accepted for funding - a rather unbelievable outcome. In 2022, we have been in full gear to kick off these projects and mobilize all the funding that is available for user projects to drive scientific discovery.

As the Annual Report goes to press, EC-funded projects are being kicked off, we have chances to meet for real discussions at conferences and symposia, and the funding landscape looks even more exciting with lots of new inspiring call openings literally on the Horizon (Europe).

The European Commission has ambitious plans to develop European science and we are delighted that employing the Research Infrastructures maximally is part of that plan.

Hence, we come out of the pandemic strengthened, not weakened. We know more

about many things than before the pandemic, with significantly more funding to serve the large community of scientists that need excellent imaging services to make a real difference in discoveries and innovations.

There is a dark cloud over Europe, but in dire times science and culture have always provided important means to connect countries and people.

We wish all users and Nodes much success when exploring the invisible world for all things unknown.

“European science is thriving and the future for research infrastructures looks bright. Our task at Euro-BioImaging is to make the best out of these favorable circumstances and help scientists to produce excellent science that will generate both impact and secure a better future.”

- John Eriksson,
Director General

COVID-19

INVESTIGATING SARS-COV-2 SPREAD IN AIRWAY TISSUE

The SARS-CoV-2 virus infects the airways, but to understand exactly how the virus spreads on a cellular level, the team around Harald Wodrich from the University of Bordeaux and his colleagues Marie-Line Andreola and Thomas Trian, used bronchial epithelia samples infected with the virus. Using immunohistochemistry and confocal microscopy, supported by the Bordeaux Imaging Center, part of the **French Bio-Imaging Node**, they were able to show how infection initiated in multiciliated bronchial cells and that in the course of the infection these cells fused with basal cells to form syncytia. These cell-fusions were released from the airway epithelium and thus may contribute to the virus spreading. Fascinatingly, they observed that some epithelia were

intrinsically resistant to infection with the virus. Using measurements of interferon production, the researchers could show a correlation between resistance to infection and fast release of type-III interferon, a type of anti-viral protein produced by cells.

Beucher et al., *bioRxiv*, 2021
<https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.05.28.446159>

A Covid-infected syncytium (green) extruding from the bronchial epithelia cell layer (red).

CHEST CT OF PULMONARY ARTERY ENLARGEMENT ALLOWS PREDICTING THE OVERALL SURVIVAL IN COVID-19 PATIENTS

At the San Raffaele Hospital (**MultiModal Molecular Imaging Italian Node**), a cohort study on 1,469 consecutive COVID-19 patients submitted to chest CT within 72h from admission was conducted in seven tertiary level hospitals in Northern Italy. The study showed that the enlargement of the main pulmonary artery diameter (MPAD) is associated with a higher rate of in-hospital mortality among COVID-19 patients. Furthermore, the statistical adjustment for demographics and comorbidities suggested that the observed phenomenon is likely an acute complication of COVID-19 pneumonia.

The MPAD can be easily and quickly measured on chest CT, without the need for any dedicated software, and could be a useful quantitative

marker to be integrated into models for risk stratification. Moreover, the detection of enlarged MPAD on chest CT may have a potential impact on patient management and treatment.

A. Esposito et al, *Eur. Rediol.* 2021
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-07622-x>

Exemplifying cases: a survivor (top) and non-survivor (bottom) patients.

CANCER

IMAGING BREAKS IN SINGLE DNA STRANDS TO STUDY DNA REPAIR PROCESSES

Many cancer cells have defective DNA repair mechanisms, leading to more mutations, but one clinically approved treatment - PARP inhibitors - targets exactly this defective DNA repair mechanism to kill the cancer cells. While the clinical use of PARP inhibitors is well established, an exact understanding of PARP function was lacking. Researchers in the lab of Hana Hanzlikova at the Laboratory of Genome Dynamics, worked with the Electron Microscopy Core Facility of the Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences (IMG CAS), part of the **Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node in Prague**, to answer this question.

They found that Okazaki fragments, intermediates of regular DNA replication, are detected by PARP1, and are therefore likely the source of the lethality of PARP

inhibitors in cancer cells. Using transmission electron microscopy to visualize individual DNA strands allowed this discovery. It is challenging the text book view of DNA replication and explaining the mechanism of action of a common anti-cancer drug.

Vaitsiankova et al, *Nat Struct Mol Biol* 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41594-022-00747-1>

A single DNA strand captured in TEM with breaks highlighted by the arrows.

PHOSPHOLIPID IMAGING TO PREDICT INEFFECTIVE CHEMOTHERAPY

At the **Dutch High Field MR Hub Node**, a clinical high field ³¹P MRSI study was performed, to identify phospholipids and to explore the potential of this biomarker for monitoring the response to cancer treatments. The method, first tested on 50 patients with breast cancer, makes it possible to predict chemotherapy efficacy based on the phosphomonoesters to phosphodiester ratio (PME/PDE) in the primary tumor.

Results were then extended to other types of cancer (lung, pancreas and liver). Also other

energy metabolites like ATP, Phosphocreatine and inorganic phosphate, as well as the acidity of the tissue, could be assessed.

D.W.J. Klomp et al, *NMR Biomed.* 2019
<https://doi.org/10.1002/nbm.4086>

A, T1 weighted 3D FFE image with a representation of the selected voxel (blue square) for ³¹P analysis. B, the corresponding T2 weighted spectrum shows all nine fitted metabolites.

NEUROSCIENCE

UNDERSTANDING LONG-TERM MEMORY AND NEURONAL PLASTICITY AT THE ULTRASTRUCTURAL LEVEL

Dendritic spines - small protrusions of neuronal membrane - contain the majority of synapses in the brain and therefore centrally contribute to brain function from ensuring stability of long-term memories to supporting neuronal plasticity and learning. Understanding spine structure and volume, as well as detecting the presence of pre- and post-synaptic structures requires highly specialized methods which allow data to be gathered at highest resolution and across a tissue volume at the same time. Serial Block-Face Scanning Electron Microscopy (SBEM) is just the right technique to address this question, and the team at the Laboratory of Imaging Tissue Structure and Function at the Nencki Institute of Experimental Biology, part of the Euro-BioImaging **Advanced Light Microscopy**

A LINK BETWEEN SYNAPTIC PLASTICITY AND REORGANIZATION OF BRAIN ACTIVITY IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE

The link between synaptic plasticity and reorganization of brain activity in health and disease is still unclear. In Parkinson's disease (PD) functional up-regulation of postsynaptic D2 receptors has been documented while its significance at the neural activity level has never been identified. At the University of Coimbra, the **Brain Imaging Network Node's** staff combined ¹¹C-raclopride PET molecular imaging of dopamine D2 receptors and functional MRI to identify molecular mechanisms at the basis of functional reorganization in Parkinson's Disease. A tight link between functional activation and synaptic changes at the molecular level was found. This paves the way for future work to understand the limited

Node Poland in Warsaw, are experts in applying SBEM for neuroscience research questions. They shared the highly specialized protocols and tips and tricks for sample preparation and running SBEM experiments in a recent JOVE neuroscience paper.

Śliwińska et al., *J. Vis. Exp.*, 2021
<https://doi.org/10.3791/62712>

3D reconstruction of a SBEM volume showing a part of a neuron with dendritic spines branching of it.

reorganization of functional networks in the brain in neurological disorders.

M. Castelo Branco et al, *PNAS* 2021
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2013962118>;
Also mentioned in *Science* 2021, 371, 689

Examples of functional magnetic imaging statistical activation maps, used to localize the frontal eye field and parietal eye field in a healthy (Top) and in an on-medication PD participant.

PLANT BIOLOGY

FLIPPED MICROSCOPES TO STUDY PLANT GROWTH

Imaging living plants as they grow has traditionally been very difficult as almost all microscopes place the sample horizontally but plants grow vertically. This challenge has been overcome by scientists at Austria's Institute of Science and Technology, part of **Austrian BioImaging/CMI Node**. With a "special" confocal microscope for vertical sample mounting and integrated directional illumination, combined with a custom software for tracking moving objects, live plant imaging becomes easy. The first version of the flipped microscope made use of custom adaptor plates to position the microscope, as well as in-house developed scripts that allowed to stabilize the acquired images of the growing root over time while recording its displacement.

Recent developments have seen the system be upgraded and it now has different holders, additional microfluidics and rotational stages, a light stimulation accessory and a second

DIGITAL PLANT IMAGING AT DIGITAL IMAGING MULTIMODAL PLATFORM NEUROMED

A user of the **DIMP Neuromed Node** used micro-PET/CT on sprouts of zucchini (*Cucurbita pepo* L., var. Genovese), aiming at verifying how saline stress affects the flow in the plant's vascular system. The oval-shaped bundle of the phloem/xylem in the stem was imaged at different positions, verifying that the minimal and maximal axis, as well as the thickness of the vascular system, have a regular growth of few hundred micrometers per day in normal plants, while they have a very large fluctuation in stressed plants. This observation may indicate that saline stress adversely impacts the regular development of the vascular system.

system with sub-diffraction limited imaging resolution modality has been added to the facility.

A similar toppled microscope system with Airyscan capabilities is available at the Czech Republic's Institute of Experimental Botany, part of Euro-BioImaging's **Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague**.

A flipped microscope imaging plant samples in an upright sample holder. Copyright: IST Austria

Moreover, a transport recovery mechanism in stressed plants was evidenced, resulting in faster PET tracer propagation speed with respect to normal plants. (Article under review)

Early stress detection by computed tomography.

IMAGE DATA

TISSUUMAPS: VISUALIZATION TOOL FOR SPATIAL-OMICS DATA

Investigation and interpretation of multimodal omics datasets often requires visual exploration of data for quality control, and constructing and validating hypotheses. However, the complexity and scale of data often makes visual exploration fundamentally challenging.

To handle, visualize and interpret such rich and complex datasets, experts from SciLife Lab - Bioimage Informatics Facility at Uppsala University, part of our **Swedish NMI Node**, support maintenance and continuous development of TissUUmeps; a browser-based tool for GPU- accelerated visualization and exploration of 10^7+ of data points overlaying a tissue sample. It enables visualization of markers and regions, exploration of spatial statistics and quantitative analyses of tissue morphology, and assessment of quality of

decoding in-situ transcriptomics data. TissUUmeps provides instant multi-resolution image viewing, can be customized, shared, and integrated in Jupyter Notebooks, opening up for unique quality control capabilities and FAIR data and workflow sharing. Read more: <https://tissuumaps.github.io/>

Cell-type signatures in the developmental human heart visualized in TissUUmeps

USING FAIR IMAGE DATA TO STUDY STRUCTURAL BRAIN CHANGES

Intracranial arteriosclerosis has been increasingly recognized as a risk factor for cognitive impairment and even dementia. A possible mechanism linking them involves structural brain changes including cerebral small vessel disease (CSVD). To assess whether intracranial arteriosclerosis is related to CSVD, a team of expert researchers led by Daniel Bos, at the Erasmus Medical Center, Rotterdam, associated with our **Population Imaging Flagship Node**, looked into the long standing population-based Rotterdam Elderly Study.

The researchers used intracranial carotid artery calcification and vertebrobasilar artery calcification, as proxies for intracranial arteriosclerosis, and performed these computed tomography (CT) based age-

adjusted measurements on 1,489 participants from within the study. Longitudinal MRI data was used to assess whether a larger calcification burden accelerates structural brain changes and for brain atrophy measures, T1-weighted, proton density weighted, and FLAIR scans were used.

While a larger calcification burden was found to be associated with an increase of CSVD markers accelerating over time it was not significantly ($p > 0.05$) associated with accelerated brain atrophy itself, leading to the conclusion that arteriosclerosis is related to accelerating structural brain changes over time. Along with the multitude of crucial observations already made, based on the Rotterdam Study, this work reiterates the importance of FAIR image data.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2021.04.005>

OTHER RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY TOPICS

CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE

ASSESSMENT OF EFFICACY OF SACUBITRIL/VALSARTAN FOR TREATING HEART FAILURE WITH PRESERVED EJECTION FRACTION

At the University of Oslo, a preclinical study on the effects of drugs used for the treatment of heart failure was carried out. In this study, Sacubitril/valsartan (sac/val) efficiency was evaluated in a pressure overload rat model of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF). The **NORMOLIM Node** contributed to the research by providing advanced MRI techniques such as Tissue Phase Mapping, to assess the drugs' effects on cardiac dysfunction and remodelling. It was shown that sac/val reduced hypertrophy compared with valsartan alone and ameliorated diastolic dysfunction, supporting the notion that sac/val

most likely holds the largest therapeutic potential in HFpEF, while still having favourable effects in cardiovascular disease with a normal range EF.

E.S. Nordèn et al, ESC Heart Failure 2021
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ehf2.13177>

Representative mid-ventricular short axis images from Cine magnetic resonance imaging: 1. untreated; 2. sac/val; 3. val; 4. control.

INFLAMMATION

A NEW PET LIGAND TARGETING VASCULAR ADHESION PROTEIN 1 FOR IMAGING INFLAMMATION

At the University of Turku, part of the **Finnish Biomedical Imaging Node**, a new PET tracer, namely ^{68}Ga -DOTA-Siglec-9, was developed. This tracer was designed to target the Vascular Adhesion Protein-1 (VAP-1) in vasculature at sites of inflammation, through Sialic acid-binding immunoglobulinlike lectin 9 (Siglec-9) peptides. Then, a first clinical study on six healthy subjects investigated the safety, tolerability, biodistribution, and radiation dosimetry of this radiopharmaceutical. Furthermore, PET scans of a patient with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) were performed to compare the efficiency of the new tracer with that of ^{18}F -FDG in detecting arthritis. ^{68}Ga -DOTA-Siglec-9 was comparable to ^{18}F -

FDG in detecting arthritis and well tolerated by all subjects. Furthermore, biodistribution was favorable for testing of the tracer in larger groups of patients with rheumatoid arthritis, as is planned for the next phase of clinical trials.

J. Knuuti et al, J. Nucl. Med. 2021
<https://dx.doi.org/10.2967/jnumed.120.250696>

^{68}Ga -DOTA-Siglec-9 PET/CT image of hands of 49 year-old patient with early RA.

MARINE BIOLOGY

TAKING MICROSCOPES UNDERWATER TO STUDY MARINE SYSTEMS IN SITU

Studying marine organisms in the native environment is key to understanding their biology as well as how they are affected by increased stress in the ocean. The VISEAON lab of Tali Treibitz at the University of Haifa, part of our **Israel BioImaging Node**, works on developing imaging systems for underwater imaging and microscopy as well as the dedicated image analysis tools for underwater images. Included in their arsenal is an underwater microscope, a system capable of non-invasively imaging seafloor environments and organisms at nearly micrometre resolution with a computationally extended depth of field, first described in *Nature Communications* (2016), “Underwater microscopy for in situ studies of benthic ecosystems”.

Since then, the Treibitz lab has worked on tools for coral segmentation, reef mapping and underwater image reconstruction, developing crucial tools to fill the gap in underwater image data.

Yuval et al., MDPI, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13040659>

A diver checks the underwater imaging system. Photo courtesy of Viseaon Marine Imaging Lab.

FOOD MICROSCOPY

ADVANCING SUPER-RESOLUTION MICROSCOPY TO VISUALIZE FOOD OXIDATION

Tracking changes in food systems using microscopy can be a key contribution in understanding and improving their stability, contributing to less food spoilage. Turbidity poses a major challenge to this microscopic characterisation of foods, particularly those containing oil-water emulsions. The team of Johannes Hohlbein at Wageningen University, the site of our **Wageningen Imaging and Spectroscopy Hub**, adapted a super-resolution open hardware microscopy framework, miCube, that they developed, to address these challenges using adaptive optics and beam shaping. These developments allowed them to use super-resolution on a model system for oil-water emulsions, made of phosvitin residing on a water-oil interface. Phosvitin is a component of egg yolk and

binds ferric ions which play a critical role in food oxidation. The adapted systems allowed them to visualize droplets with sub 100 nm resolution. Details on the technical developments are published in their recent paper:

Jabermoradi et al., Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A, 2022
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0164>

Super-resolution image of oil droplets with phosvitin on their surface.

TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENTS

NEW AND IMPROVED CALCIUM SENSORS

Calcium has many important functions inside cells and therefore measuring calcium has long been a central goal of functional imaging. Many different genetically encoded calcium indicators exist, but they share shortcomings - their intensity-based readout hinders quantification and they are often pH sensitive, making true quantitative imaging of calcium challenging. To address these issues, the group of Joachim Goedhart, together with the team of the **Functional Imaging Flagship Node at the Van Leeuwenhoek Center for Advanced Microscopy (LCAM)** in Amsterdam, developed the Tq-Ca-FLITS biosensor. Tq-Ca-FLITS is a unique calcium indicator that functions due to conformational changes of the fluorescent protein that directly affects quantum yield and fluorescence lifetime. To show the functionality of their new sensor, reported in a paper in *Nature Communications*, the team

measured calcium concentrations in organelles and in endothelial cells. This shows that the sensor is highly functional for the quantitative measurements of dynamic calcium concentration changes that are required to understand cellular processes.

van der Linden et al., Nature Communications, 2021
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27249-w>

A selection of newly synthesized probes. Image credit: Joachim Goedhart

SCIENTIFIC CURIOSITIES

THE COELACANTH: A TRUE LAZARUS SPECIES

Once thought to have been extinct for 66 million years, the coelacanth sent shock waves through the scientific community when a live, large specimen (1–2 m, ~90 kg) was discovered in South Africa in 1938. The global interest was further sparked by the view that coelacanths represented the closest relative to tetrapods. This “living fossil” provides important cues to e.g. the early evolutionary transition from fins to legs and the evolution of lungs.

Coelacanths have among the lowest metabolic rates of all vertebrates. Using high resolution x-ray computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging, the researchers

at the Aarhus University, **Danish BioImaging Node**, have shown that they regulate their buoyancy and balance by fine tuning their body constituents to minimize the required energy to keep station and keep in balance. *(Work in progress)*

The Coelacanth, as seen with X-ray computed tomography. Imaging work done by Dr Henrik Lauridsen and his team, in Michael Pedersen's Group, at the Aarhus University, Danish BioImaging Node.

FROM OUR NODES

ABOUT OUR NODES

Euro-Biolmaging is a distributed infrastructure - our central activities are coordinated by our 3 Hub sites, but services are provided in the imaging facilities called “Nodes.” By becoming a Euro-Biolmaging Node, imaging facilities agree to provide Open Access to technologies, services and expertise to all Euro-Biolmaging users, independent of where the users come from, their field of research or their level of expertise.

EXPANDING INFRASTRUCTURE

In 2021, we welcomed eight new Nodes and one Node upgraded to the Euro-Biolmaging family. These new Nodes included two Mixed, five Biomedical, and one Biological Imaging Node. New Nodes are located in the Czech Republic, Denmark, Hungary, Israel, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, and Portugal. This scaling of our Node family is key, as the new Nodes bring on board a vast array of expertise, scientific excellence and help us grow the portfolio of imaging technologies available in open access to the Euro-Biolmaging users.

“Our Nodes are very diverse, but what they have in common is their dedication to high-quality imaging technologies and supporting their users in their research.”

- Antje Keppler,
Bio-Hub Section Director

To welcome the new Nodes into the Euro-Biolmaging family and ensure that they are informed about the opportunities available to all Node staff via Euro-Biolmaging, the Euro-Biolmaging Hub team engaged with the new Nodes via “Onboarding” meetings in 2021. These online meetings brought Node and Hub staff together, to exchange about the opportunities and obligations of being a Euro-Biolmaging Node and learn about specific services and expertise of our new family members. In addition, new Nodes were invited to present their facilities and expertise at the Euro-Biolmaging Virtual Pub.

In the following pages, learn more about our vibrant Node community and see how they have adapted to the pandemic context. Despite the challenges, they continue to share their passion for science and learning with users, colleagues, and the general public and support their users in producing outstanding science.

SNAPSHOTS

AUSTRIA

Scanning Electron Microscopy at USTEM, part of Austrian Biomaging CMI Node. Copyright USTEM (2020)

BULGARIA

The team at Sofia Biomaging Node helps users to understand DNA damage and underlying cell biologic processes.

CZECHIA

The IMG facility at our Prague Node has acquired new instruments for specialized sample preparation for transmission electron microscopy (TEM). They also have a TESCAN Amber Cryo (cryo FIB-SEM workstation), which was lent to the IMG by TESCAN in the frame of a scientific partnership, to support cryogenic applications.

DENMARK

Colleagues from our new Danish Biomaging Node show off their new T-shirts.

PORTUGAL

It was a great year for our Portuguese Brain Imaging Network Node. Here, a photo of their upgraded human PET machine.

FINLAND

Visitors at the Electron Microscopy Unit (EMBI) in Helsinki, Finland, one of the units forming the Finnish Advanced Light Microscopy Node (FiALM). Picture by Eija Jokitalo.

HUNGARY

Upgrade of PicoQuant FLIM microscope with TimeHarp unit and incubator box in Debrecen, part of Cellular Imaging Hungary Node.

ISRAEL

A typical day at Israel Biomaging, a multi-sited, multi-modal Node including 7 sites across Israel with a range of technologies for biological, molecular to medical imaging.

ITALY

The coordinators of our MMMI Italian Node pose with their T-shirts.

Small animal imaging at our new Node, DIMP NEUROMED. This Node offers optical imaging, population imaging and preclinical functional imaging.

POLAND

Image analysis but also smiling faces at our new Advanced Light Microscopy Node Poland, with sites in Warsaw and Cracow.

COMMUNICATION & OUTREACH

On top of providing open access to imaging technologies and expertise, our Nodes are also incredibly active in communication and outreach. They interact regularly with the general public to educate on the importance of a knowledge-based approach to science and the significance of imaging to basic research, human health and diagnostics. Here is a small selection from events that were held in 2021.

#EuropeanResearchersNight

SEPTEMBER 2021

PORTUGAL

Scientists from the CCMAR, part of Portuguese Platform of BioImaging, our Portuguese Node, enticed their local community in Algarve with a “3D microscope with a mobile phone” in an event entitled, “Science for All.”

ITALY

NOTTE EUROPEA DEI RICERCATORI

DIMP NEUROMED Node organized livestream visits of the imaging infrastructure that included presentations by researchers.

ITALY

Staff of the Multi Modal Molecular Imaging (MMMI) Italian Node were at the Molecular Biotechnology Center in Torino, Italy, to show “How the invisible can be made visible.” Research results were presented in a simple, eye-catching way, with fun activities on the principles of imaging.

FINLAND

In Turku, Finland, Guillaume Jacquemet of the Cell Migration Lab presented a video to show how imaging work done at the Finnish ALM Node supports his research on cancer in a multidisciplinary exhibition entitled “Forcing the Impossible.”

CZECHIA

The electron microscopy facility from Biological Center at České Budějovice, part of our Prague Node, participated in Czech European Researchers' Night, which is an open excursion for students and public.

HUNGARY

The ELKH Szeged Biological Research Centre, part of Cellular Imaging Hungary, organized hand's on microscopy event for school children as well as laboratory visits.

#BrainAwareness

FINLAND

The Finnish Biomedical Imaging Node provided virtual visits to different parts of the NeuroImaging infrastructure. In total, 200 spectators (7 virtual visits), including grade school, high-school and university students.

ITALY

The Italian ALM Node participated in the European Researchers' Night in Florence with a talk titled: “To the discovery of the human brain”.

HUNGARY

A unique research center of international significance, “Brain Vision Center”, was established in Budapest in collaboration with our Cellular Imaging Hungary Node.

#CNRSInsolite

OCTOBER 2021

In October 2021, the Institut Cochin imaging facility IMAG'IC, part of France-BioImaging, hosted one of the CNRS “Extraordinary Tour” for the Fête de la Science with middle school students. They had the opportunity to visit a photonic imaging facility, discover what light is, and how to tame it to image cells. They also built their own mini optical microscope “Foldscope”, adaptable to a smartphone.

FRANCE

Foldscope “atelier.” Photo CNRS.

FROM THE BENCH TO THE CLASSROOM AND BACK AGAIN...

NETHERLANDS

Facility of Multimodal Imaging - AMMI Maastricht spoke with students from an elementary school in Maastricht on the topic, “Do you want to become a researcher?”

CZECHIA

The Advanced Light Microscopy and Medical Imaging Brno Node participated in the Open Doors Days at ISI for two days in the autumn, with around 500 visitors coming from secondary schools, universities and the general public.

NETHERLANDS

The Van Leeuwenhoek Center for Advanced Microscopy (LCAM) - Functional Imaging Flagship Node Amsterdam welcomed 20 high school students for a 2-day Master class on Fluorescence Microscopy.

Dr. Berta-Cillero Pastor and Dr. Benjamin Balluff from the AMMI Maastricht Node speak to elementary students in the classroom.

NETHERLANDS

Erasmus MC OIC - Advanced Light Microscopy Rotterdam Node gave two guest lessons to fifth grade students at Marnix Gymnasium (grammar school) then one week later brought a group of students to visit the OIC and have a tour with hands-on-experience.

REMOTE ACCESS & TRAINING

60%

OF EURO-BIOIMAGING
NODES OFFERED REMOTE OR
HYBRID COURSES IN 2021

Faced with unprecedented restrictions and challenges in 2020, we witnessed the remarkable resilience of our Nodes, as they quickly adapted to the pandemic situation in order to continue to provide user services and contribute to scientific discovery. Many of the “emergency procedures” implemented by our Nodes in 2020 were included in routine procedure in 2021, such as remote access to workstations at the Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Bio-Imaging Centre (Alembic) in Milan, part of our ALM Italian Node. Remote user projects are common at many of our Nodes, and remote or “hybrid” training courses are increasingly popular.

Some of the advantages of remote training include greater inclusiveness, greater geographic diversity, and great availability of trainers. In these pages, we highlight some of the innovative solutions our Nodes implemented to continue to provide training and user access despite the pandemic uncertainty.

NORWAY

6TH NORMIC IMAGING WORKSHOP

The NorMIC Node organized a fully remote course in Advanced Light Microscopy and Image Processing in May 2021. Over 70 students - including 30 located outside of Norway - took advantage of this course. It was challenging to host this many people remotely for “hands on” coursework but it was very successful. The geographical diversity of instructors and students was highly appreciated. The Node is now investing in the IT infrastructure necessary to continue with this type of event in the future.

DENMARK

“Virtual user trainings are useful learning for us - more users are able to participate and see what goes on. Core Facility staff don't have to repeat as many times the same basic concepts and focus more on experimental specifics in the one-to-one trainings.”

- Nynne Christensen,
Facility Manager, CAB, UCPH, Danish
BioImaging

EMBL

The Electron Microscopy Core Facility at EMBL organized its first virtual EMBO Practical Course: In Situ CLEM at room temperature and in cryo. Although weary in the beginning about going virtual, the event turned out to be a huge success because of the trainers, the highly motivated students and amazing support (technical & otherwise) throughout the course. The “From 3D light to 3D electron microscopy” workshop was also run virtually in 2021. A fantastic speaker line-up and demonstrations, given by the trainers at the different sites, of techniques used widely in the field made this meeting a huge success. Photos by Elisabeth Zielonka, courtesy of the EICAT team.

PORTUGAL

Our PPBI Node experimented with many training course formats, from hybrid (on site + broadcasting) to the highly successful outdoor classroom (Introduction to Image Analysis course, July 2021). They also organized full online Microscopy, Tissue clearing and Image Analysis courses with high national and international participation. Photo G. Martins/JGC.

FINLAND

Camilo Guzman of the Finnish Advanced Light Microscopy Node with remote user from Vienna, Austria (Razieh Khoshnevisan - Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft). The user visited the Node for 2 weeks, but continued to use the STED system remotely with support from Node staff.

FRANCE

The France-BioImaging WP on Multiscale Light Sheet Imaging organized a first online training on Light-Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy (LSFM) in February 2021. 317 people registered for the training and 85 attended the Q&A interactive session. Sessions were made available on YouTube. In contrast, the Super Resolution course from BIC Bordeaux (pictured above) was held in person in September 2021. Photo: Magali Mondin/ Twitter @BIC_Bordeaux

CZECHIA

In Brno, the MAFIL facility organized a hybrid Neuroimaging course for the first time in 2021. It was more complicated to organize than an on-site or remote event, but more pleasant than purely remote. Advantages include combining onsite presenters with one remote presenter and one lecture based on pre-recorded presentation.

NETHERLANDS

MIDOG 2021
Mitosis Domain Generalization Challenge
part of MICCAI 2021

MIDOG Preliminary Test Phase (CLOSED) | MIDOG Final Test Phase (CLOSED)

MIDOG Final Test Phase (CLOSED) Leaderboard

#	User (Team)	Algorithm	Created	Score	Publication / Project
1st	AI.medical (AI.medical)	mitosis	3 Sept. 2021	0.7474	
2nd	medcomp (ETAC Center)	Hybrid Method	3 Sept. 2021	0.7474	
3rd	guytonlab (Dermatology)	V_Anet	4 Sept. 2021	0.7381	
4th	pharmSIS (SIS)	MIDOG baseline - mid	3 Sept. 2021	0.7343	
5th	medcomp (ETAC Center)	MIDOG Reference Test Algorithm	26 Aug. 2021	0.7308	
6th	medcomp (ETAC Center)	MIDOG Ref	26 Aug. 2021	0.7288	

On October 19 and November 2, the Challenges Framework Flagship Node hosted an online workshop on how to create and host an algorithm container on Grand Challenge. The event was very well received with almost 50 participants.

AUSTRIA

AUSTRIAN BIOIMAGING/CMI

Node contact: Wolfgang J. Weninger (Wolfgang.Weninger@meduniwien.ac.at), Baubak Bajoghli (Baubak.Bajoghli@vbcf.ac.at)

Website: www.bioimaging-austria.at

12

FACILITIES

200

EXTERNAL USERS

<100,000

USAGE HOURS

10M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

40

STAFF INVOLVED

<5

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- Many facility heads are involved in teaching - with an emphasis on bioimaging.
- The Node is preparing a Master's Degree in Biomedical Imaging.
- In 2021, Austrian BioImaging/CMI chaired the EU ACTION COMULIS: www.comulis.eu building a European community for correlative multimodal imaging. COMULIS offers funding opportunities for Correlated Multimodality Imaging projects.

CZECHIA

ADVANCED LIGHT AND ELECTRON MICROSCOPY NODE PRAGUE CZ

Node contact: info.praguenode@czech-bioimaging.cz

Website: www.czech-bioimaging.cz/euro-bi

5

FACILITIES

265

EXTERNAL USERS

37,569

USAGE HOURS

27.2M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

28

STAFF INVOLVED

17

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- The LM facility at IMG organized the first EMBO Course on Super-Resolution in LIGHT Microscopy in Central and East Europe.
- IPHYS Bioimaging Facility participates in Czech-Slovenian project "Changes of neuro-musculo-fascial system in diabetes analyzed by 3D microscopy and biomechanic tests".
- František Kitzberger, a staff member of the EM facility at České Budějovice, obtained a Thermo Fisher Scientific and ČSMS 2021 stipend grant.

New instruments:

- Leica Stellaris 8 FALCON with DLS and FCS modularity, Zeiss LSM 900 with Airyscan2 and Multiplex, Leica THUNDER Imager (EM Cryo CLEM), Zeiss Elyra 7, Nikon CSU-W1, Nanolive CX-A, Jeol JEM-1400.

BULGARIA

SOFIA BIOIMAGING NODE

Node contact: Stoyno Stoynov (stoynov@bio21.bas.bg)

Website: dnarepair.bas.bg/eurobioimaging.bg/site/

1

FACILITIES

6

EXTERNAL USERS

4,300

USAGE HOURS

2.1M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

9

STAFF INVOLVED

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node moved to a new building, specially designed to house a microscopy center.
- Funding received for six Bulgarian users whose projects will successfully pass the Euro-BioImaging external evaluation (projects to be carried out in 2022).
- 3 new instruments were installed or purchased in 2021, expanding capacity and technologies available to users to include FLIM, FCS and anisotropy applications.

CZECHIA

ADVANCED LIGHT MICROSCOPY AND MEDICAL IMAGING NODE BRNO CZ

Node contact: Michal Mikl (michal.mikl@ceitec.muni.cz)

Website: www.czech-bioimaging.cz/euro-bi

4

FACILITIES

38

EXTERNAL USERS

14,081

USAGE HOURS

14.2M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

23.25

STAFF INVOLVED

7

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- Human MRI Lab (MAFIL) purchased LCD glasses for MRI visual stimulation. CELLIM facility purchased new Zeiss Lightsheet 7 for aqueous and cleared samples. Experimental Biophotonics Facility purchased major upgrade of Q-Phase system.
- 2 GACR grants received for 2022-2024 (1 PI, 1 co-PI), as well as grant from Technology Agency of Czech Republic in collaboration with industry for development of next generation holographic microscope to be available in our facility.
- Participation in Horizon 2020 Marie-Sklodowska-Curie project, INSPiRE-MED, dedicated to MR spectroscopy.

CZECHIA

CENTER FOR ADVANCED PRECLINICAL IMAGING (CAPI)

Node contact: : Ludek Sefc
sefc@cesnet.cz

Website: www.capi.lf1.cuni.cz/en

1

FACILITIES

17

EXTERNAL
USERS

1,333

USAGE
HOURS

6.4M

INVESTMENTS
IN
INSTRUMENTS

10

STAFF
INVOLVED

1

TRAINING
COURSES
ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node contributes to the Thyropix project, funded by TAČR, to develop an advanced imaging system dedicated primarily to thyroid gland monitoring: www.thyropix.com
- The Node is also involved in the Neurophage project, supported by JPND, to explore innovative therapeutic strategies for Parkinson's Disease: www.neurodegenerationresearch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Project-NEUROPHAGE.pdf

New instruments:

- 7T MRI - installed on May 2021: MRS*DRYMAG 7.0T (MR Solutions, GB)

EMBL

EURO-BIOIMAGING EMBL-NODE

Node contact: Rainer Pepperkok
EuBI-EMBL-Node@embl.org

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/advanced-light-microscopy-facility-embl

3

FACILITIES

73

EXTERNAL
USERS

65,604

USAGE
HOURS

23M

INVESTMENTS
IN
INSTRUMENTS

18

STAFF
INVOLVED

6

TRAINING
COURSES
ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node was very involved in virtual training, conferences & courses – including an online EMBO Practical course, several virtual courses with industry partners and the highly successful online “From 3D light to 3D electron microscopy workshop.”
- CZI imaging scientist grant to Christian Tischer (ALMF/CBA).

New instruments:

- **ALMF:** Zeiss LSM 980 AIRY fast, Leica Stellaris 8 TauSens, Abbelight safe 360, Nikon spinning disk
- **EMCF:** EM Trim2 to automatically trim resin blocks for sectioning, JEOL1400 Flash electron microscope
- **MIF:** Olympus FV3000 confocal

DENMARK

DANISH BIOIMAGING

Node contact: Thomas Braunstein
(thobra@sund.ku.dk), Nynne Christensen
(nmchristensen@bio.ku.dk) & Clara Prats
(cprats@sund.ku.dk)

Website: www.danishbioimaging.dk

5

FACILITIES

161

EXTERNAL
USERS

36,129

USAGE
HOURS

25.8M

INVESTMENTS
IN
INSTRUMENTS

18.5

STAFF
INVOLVED

14

TRAINING
COURSES
ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- Carlsberg Foundation infrastructure support for accessory equipment to live imaging at CAB; Novo Nordisk Foundation Infrastructure Grant BioDEEP (2M euros to implement SPIM) at CFIM; Danish Research Council, Novo Nordisk Foundation, and Lundbeck Foundation funding at AU pre-clinical facility.

New instruments:

- 3i spinning disk confocal, Leica Stellaris 8, Zeiss Light Sheet 7, LSM900, LSM980, Photostimulation upgrade at Multiphoton, Upgrade of Edinburgh Instruments FLS 980 spectrometer, 1 OCT system, 1 hyper-polarized MRI system.

FINLAND

FINNISH ADVANCED LIGHT MICROSCOPY NODE

Node contact: Camilo Guzmán
camilo.guzman@abo.fi

Website: www.eurobioimaging.fi/FiALM

6

FACILITIES

80

EXTERNAL
USERS

60,000

USAGE
HOURS

16.5M

INVESTMENTS
IN
INSTRUMENTS

35

STAFF
INVOLVED

6

TRAINING
COURSES
ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node worked on a number of grants awarded by the Academy of Finland (AoF) iCOIN, AoF Flagships (Gene, Cell, Nano), AoF FIRI 2020, Cancer Society; AoF Program “Health from science”.

New instruments:

- **Turku:** Fluidigm AccuLift™ LCM microscope, Hyperion Imaging mass cytometry system
- **Helsinki:** Robotic hand, incubator, and high content screening microscope, Zeiss Crossbeam 550 FIB-SEM; Leica EM TP (automated tissue processor for plastic embedding)
- **Oulu:** Zeiss AxioZoom V16, Apotome 3 microscope

FINLAND

FINNISH BIOMEDICAL IMAGING NODE

Node contact:

contact-fibi@eurobioimaging.fi

Website: www.eurobioimaging.fi/FiBI/

HIGHLIGHTS

- Finnish BioImaging Opening Seminar was held in June 2021.
- The Node received 5.1M euros of investment, including 2.5M euros from Academy of Finland.
- Virtual visits of the NEUROIMAGING infrastructure attracted a total of 200 spectators including many students.

New instruments:

- Siemens Vision PET/CT; MR Solutions µPET/MRI; MEG upgrade; Navigated TMS upgrade; MEG peripheral instrumentation renewal; Two 128-ch EEG systems for use with and without simultaneous MEG in EU-funded research project AI-Mind; VR-1 virtual reality system; BioTek Synergy multimodal plate reader, incubator for radioactive cell uptake studies, Canon/Arcoma Intuition digital radiography system, Canon CXDI flat panel detectors.

4

FACILITIES

195

EXTERNAL USERS

22,960

USAGE HOURS

35M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

40+

STAFF INVOLVED

16

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

FRANCE

FRENCH BIOIMAGING NODE

Node contact:

contact@france-bioimaging.org

Website: www.france-bioimaging.org

HIGHLIGHTS

- The H2P2 histopathology platform located in Rennes (France-BioImaging Bretagne-Loire Node) became the European reference for Leica's multiplexed imaging solution Cell DIVE, which is of particular interest in Cancer treatment research.
- The Node organized a number of online training courses and shared them on the FBI YouTube Channel.
- FBI launched its first "FBI Internal Call 2021: Technology transfer from the R&D teams to the core facilities" to promote the transfer of new technologies (instrumentation, probes, staining methods, software, data analysis or data visualization) from the R&D teams to the facilities of FBI, for access and service to end-users.

20

FACILITIES

634

EXTERNAL USERS

85,296

USAGE HOURS

50M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

301

STAFF INVOLVED

41

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HUNGARY

CELLULAR IMAGING HUNGARY

Node contact:

szollo@med.unideb.hu

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/cellular-imaging-hungary

HIGHLIGHTS

- A unique research center of international significance, "Brain Vision Center", has been established in Budapest under the leadership of Prof. Botond Roska, a pioneer in vision restoration research, and Prof. Balázs Rózsa, founder of Femtonics Ltd. (Sub-Node of Cellular Imaging Hungary).
- Cellular Imaging Hungary Node was selected into Top 50 RI in Hungary. Prof. János Szöllősi, head of Cellular Imaging Hungary Node, received Széchenyi-Prize.

New instruments:

- **Debrecen:** Upgrade of PicoQuant FLIM microscope with TimeHarp unit and incubator box, Zeiss LSM 880 upgrade with fast Airy unit.
- **Femtonics:** High resolution stereo dissection microscope for sample preparation, upgraded software and electronics on the 3D microscope for new scanning modes.

4

FACILITIES

16

EXTERNAL USERS

14,401

USAGE HOURS

7.4M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

6

STAFF INVOLVED

6

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HUNGARY

MEDICAL AND PRECLINICAL IMAGING HUNGARY NODE

Node contact: István Hajdu,

hajdu.istvan@med.unideb.hu

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/medical-and-preclinical-imaging-hungary

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node, along with the Medical and Preclinical Imaging Hungary Node, was recognized as an Excellent Research Infrastructure in Hungary in terms of scientific performance and international collaboration. Awarded by the National Research, Development and Innovation Office Budapest, Hungary.
- The core facility's instruments moved to a newly renovated 75 m² laboratory room.
- Participated in Researcher's Night with outreach to the general public.

5

FACILITIES

16

EXTERNAL USERS

2,655

USAGE HOURS

4.5M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

6.1

STAFF INVOLVED

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

ISRAEL

ISRAEL BIOIMAGING

Node contact: Michal Neeman
michal.neeman@weizmann.ac.i

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/israel-bioimaging

HIGHLIGHTS

- Participation in 2 EU Cordis Projects under Future and Emerging Technologies.
- VATAT grant for upgrade of the MRI 9.4 Tesla around 900K USD.

New instruments:

- Codex multiplex system- Akoya; Atomic force microscope, Abbelight SAFE 360 with PRIMO biological printing, multi modality SR ELYRA SIM2 with STEDYCON microscope, high content cytation 5, Light sheet Z7 and SPIM lifecanvastech, Leica Confocal STELLARIS 5 for live imaging with 4 lasers spectral imaging, simultaneous multicolor, confocal system.

12

FACILITIES

18

EXTERNAL USERS

15,000

USAGE HOURS

N/A

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

26

STAFF INVOLVED

7

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

ITALY

ADVANCED LIGHT MICROSCOPY ITALIAN NODE

Node contact: Dr. Seetharaman Parashuraman
raman@ibbc.cnr.it

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/advanced-light-microscopy-italian-node/

HIGHLIGHTS

- **Milan:** Hosted multiple remote & hybrid training events and served as support structure in many EC grants.
- **Genova:** Hosted a long term demo of Oxgene incubator. Partner in the European project MOSBRI- Molecular-Scale Biophysics Research Infrastructure.
- **Florence:** Involved in Human Brain Project and ERC-POC DAPTOMIC and ERC BRAINBIT projects on imaging of human brain.

New instruments:

- Olympus FV 3000 RS; new HTM confocal platform (Molecular Devices ImageXpress); Leica two photon and Abberior STED super-resolution microscope; Zeiss 980 with Airy Scan and Zeiss Elyra; new NAS data storage system; hyperspectral microscope; Leica Thunder Imager 3D Cell Culture.

5

FACILITIES

103

EXTERNAL USERS

40,719

USAGE HOURS

14.1M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

27

STAFF INVOLVED

5

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

ITALY

DIGITAL IMAGING MULTIMODAL PLATFORM NEUROMED - DIMP NEUROMED

Node contact: Prof. Nicola D'Ascenzo
(nicola.dascenzo@neuromed.it),
Dr. Emilia Belfiore

Website: www.neuromed.it

HIGHLIGHTS

- NEUROMED is the coordinator of the first European consortium studying the application of PET to functional plant imaging, PETAL "Positron Emission Tomography for Agriculture and Life".
- Prof. D'Ascenzo teaches the Positron Emission Tomography course in the Master in Medical System Engineering at the University of Magdeburg, where he outlines the strength of Euro-Bioimaging and its opportunities for European and international researchers.
- NEUROMED organized the European Researchers' Night 2021 - Virtual Edition on all Social Networks (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube) with the involvement of students from high schools.

1

FACILITIES

15

EXTERNAL USERS

6,800

USAGE HOURS

2.6M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

18

STAFF INVOLVED

1

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

ITALY

MMMI - MULTI MODAL MOLECULAR IMAGING ITALIAN NODE

Node contact: Enzo Terreno
enzo.terreno@unito.it

Website: www.mmmi.unito.it

HIGHLIGHTS

- IBFM facility standardized a mouse hotel for multiple acquisition and analysis and contributed to a new atlas toolbox for mouse brain quantification compatible with SPM analysis and Allen brain atlas.
- Promoted Euro-BioImaging and MMMI at University of Milano - Bicocca and at the Biomedical Science Conference Department.
- The Node contributes to a new two-year Master Program available at the University of Torino entitled "Biotechnological and Chemical Sciences in Diagnostics".

New instruments:

- MRI Bruker Pharmascan 7 T (preclinical) (UniTO)- PET/SPECT/CT MILabs VECTor6 (preclinical) (UniTO)- IVIS Lumina Optical/X-ray (preclinical) (IBB) - Siemens Biograph Vision 450 Edge digital PET/CT (clinical) (FTGM); new fully digital PET scanner (Discovery MI system, GE) (SDN).

8

FACILITIES

31

EXTERNAL USERS

3,515

USAGE HOURS

26M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

30

STAFF INVOLVED

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

ITALY

PHASE CONTRAST IMAGING FLAGSHIP NODE TRIESTE

Node contact: Giuliana Tromba
giuliana.tromba@elettra.eu

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/phase-contrast-imaging-flagship-node-trieste

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node continued to perform some remote experiments, due to persistence of the COVID pandemic situation.
- Main technical achievement was to improve the micro CT setup control system and test implementation of an in-situ setup for the study of samples kept under pressure.
- The application of this device realized by the Politecnico di Milano made it possible to evaluate the mechanical properties of human bone samples subject to controlled increased loading. This is particularly useful in the study of disease affecting the bones such as osteoporosis. A dedicated setup, optimized for the beamline characteristics, capable to apply controlled load, tension and torsion during microCT scans is under evaluation.

1

FACILITIES

19

EXTERNAL
USERS

1,000

USAGE
HOURS

50,000

INVESTMENTS
IN
INSTRUMENTS

2

STAFF
INVOLVED

3

TRAINING
COURSES
ORGANIZED

NETHERLANDS

CHALLENGES FRAMEWORK FLAGSHIP NODE

Node contact: Bram van Ginneken
(bram.vanginneken@radboudumc.nl),
Ajay Patel (ajay.patel@radboudumc.nl)

Website: www.grand-challenge.org/

HIGHLIGHTS

- New way of running challenges on the platform leads to fairer and more objective comparison of machine learning solutions. In addition, algorithms are centrally stored and remain accessible even after the challenge is finished.
- Beginning of cloud-based services making the Grand Challenges platform more scalable.
- On October 19 and November 2, the Node hosted an online workshop on how to create and host an algorithm container on Grand Challenge. The event was very well received with almost 50 participants from both within and outside our organization.

1

FACILITIES

20,444

EXTERNAL
USERS

8,761

USAGE
HOURS

36,000

INVESTMENTS
IN
INSTRUMENTS

7

STAFF
INVOLVED

1

TRAINING
COURSES
ORGANIZED

NETHERLANDS

CORRELATIVE LIGHT ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (CLEM) DUTCH FLAGSHIP NODE

Node contact: Judith Klumperman
J.Klumperman@umcutrecht.nl

Website: www.cellbiology-utrecht.nl

HIGHLIGHTS

- Dutch CLEM Node participates in the NEMI educational platform (open resources for electron microscopy): www.sconesaboj.gitlab.io/nemi-platform/index.html
- EFRO awarded a 1.5M euros grant to a consortium including Technolution, TU Delft (Hoogenboom group) and the UMCG (Giepmans group) to develop, validate, and use a novel imaging data platform for data generated by FAST-EMs and build an atlas of human tissues at nanometer-range resolution (www.nanotomy.org).
- New Instruments: UMCG: Multibeam FAST-EM and Zeiss LS7 light sheet light microscope. UMCU: Leica EM-ICE HPF (high pressure freezer). LUMC: Talos Arctica TEM

3

FACILITIES

9

EXTERNAL
USERS

30,999

USAGE
HOURS

6M

INVESTMENTS
IN
INSTRUMENTS

5

STAFF
INVOLVED

0

TRAINING
COURSES
ORGANIZED

NETHERLANDS

ERASMUS MC OIC - ADVANCED LIGHT MICROSCOPY ROTTERDAM NODE

Node contact: Gert-Jan Kremers
G.kremers@erasmusmc.nl

Website: www.erasmusoic.nl

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node installed a confocal microscope in the radiation lab for radioactive work, e.g. following Double Strand Break repair in cells in medium with Lutetium.
- The Node gave two guest lessons for fifth graders at Marnix Grammar school and gave them a tour with hands-on-experience.
- Organization of a one week master course with lectures and hands-on sessions.

1

FACILITIES

8

EXTERNAL
USERS

N/A

USAGE
HOURS

N/A

INVESTMENTS
IN
INSTRUMENTS

8

STAFF
INVOLVED

0*

TRAINING
COURSES
ORGANIZED

* due to COVID-19

NETHERLANDS

FACILITY OF MULTIMODAL IMAGING - AMMI MAASTRICHT

Node contact: Marc A.M.J. van Zandvoort
mamj.vanzandvoort@maastrichtuniversity.nl

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/facility-of-excellence-in-imaging---alm-and-molecular-imaging-node-maastricht

HIGHLIGHTS

- In 2021, the Node was able to offer training courses & small group trainings. The data analysis course was supported by a virtual mobility grant (COMULIS).
- Participation in EU projects (EU-H2020 MSCA ITN FoodTranet, Horizon 2020 INNOSUP 956190, EU-H2020 MSCA ITN INSPIRE, COST action COMULIS COST, MSCA ITN Theradnet, Horizon 2020 ImmunoSABR).
- All staff were involved in Bachelor Biomedical sciences (BBS) program, Master of Science (MBS) program.

New instrument:

- UPLC Shimadzu for MSI, various additional equipment for Microscopy.

5

FACILITIES

46

EXTERNAL USERS

35,000

USAGE HOURS

20M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

14

STAFF INVOLVED

3

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

NETHERLANDS

DUTCH HIGH FIELD IMAGING HUB

Node contact: Dennis Klomp
d.w.j.klomp-2@umcutrecht.nl

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/dutch-high-field-imaging-hub

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node offers high field MRI infrastructure for human imaging.
- The imaging centers involved in the Node are equipped with ultra-high Field MR instruments that can be used to obtain ultra-high resolution images of the brain, spine, breast, heart, abdomen and extremities, and benefit from increased signal to noise and contrast associated with higher magnetic field strengths. The sites work together to exchange imaging protocols, data processing technology and RF coil technology to expedite the further development of high precision imaging.

5

FACILITIES

15

EXTERNAL USERS

6,470

USAGE HOURS

21M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

5

STAFF INVOLVED

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

NETHERLANDS

HIGH THROUGHPUT MICROSCOPY DUTCH FLAGSHIP NODE

Node contact: Sylvia Le Dévedec
s.e.ledevedec@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/high-throughput-microscopy-dutch-flagship-node

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node is made up of 2 sites: Leiden Cell Observatory and Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI).
- The Leiden Cell Observatory leads the EU Project RISK-HUNT3R to develop a new modular framework for animal-free next generation risk assessment (NGRA) of chemical substances.
- At NKI, all staff are involved in Track Master Oncology, University of Amsterdam

New instruments:

- At Leiden Cell Observatory: NIKON A1R LIPSI system + Incucyte S2 + compounds libraries
- At NKI: ImageXpress micro4 + oligopools sgRNAs + synthetic sgRNA collection + pooled sgRNA collections

2

FACILITIES

15

EXTERNAL USERS

10,000

USAGE HOURS

3.5M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

5

STAFF INVOLVED

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

NETHERLANDS

PRECLINICAL IMAGING CENTRE (PRIME) - MOLECULAR IMAGING DUTCH NODE

Node contact: Amanda Kiliaan
(amanda.kiliaan@radboudumc.nl),
Wilma Janssen (wilma.janssen-kessels@radboudumc.nl)

Website: www.radboudumc.nl/en/research/radboud-technology-centers/imaging/preclinical-imaging-center

HIGHLIGHTS

- Node staff lead a work package in one of the IMI2 programs: Imaging biomarkers (IBs) for safer drugs: validation of translational imaging methods in drug safety assessment (TRISTAN project: www.imi-tristan.eu). In this project they use imaging to determine the distribution of novel biologicals and perform reproducibility studies to validate imaging biomarkers in drug-induced interstitial lung disease.

New instrument:

- Acquisition of a new SPECT/CT (MILabs) and PET/CT (Inviscan) which will be installed in 2022.

1

FACILITIES

2

EXTERNAL USERS

2,350

USAGE HOURS

400,000*

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

7

STAFF INVOLVED

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

* 2020-2021

NETHERLANDS

POPULATION IMAGING FLAGSHIP NODE ROTTERDAM

Node contact:

population.imaging@gmail.com

Website: www.populationimaging.eu

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node mainly offers access to image data infrastructure, including storage, annotation, and image analysis tools.
- The Node participated in three H2020 funded projects: HealthyCloud, euCanSHare, and EuCanImage, a European Cancer Image Platform Linked to Biological and Health Data for Next-Generation Artificial Intelligence and Precision Medicine in Oncology. It leads the data management platform, including imaging data storage and development of an imaging metadata catalogue. They are involved in image data analytics, such as deep learning and radiomics. The aim is to build a federated platform for AI-analysis.

1

FACILITIES

50

EXTERNAL USERS

1,000

USAGE HOURS

1.5M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

12

STAFF INVOLVED

1

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

NETHERLANDS

THE VAN LEEUWENHOEK CENTER FOR ADVANCED MICROSCOPY (LCAM) - FUNCTIONAL IMAGING FLAGSHIP NODE AMSTERDAM

Node contact: Mark Hink

m.a.hink@uva.nl

Website: www.lcam.nl

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node published its first functional-imaging screen, a FLIM-screen for cAMP regulating enzymes (PMID: 34671065) and a turquoise fluorescence lifetime-based biosensor for quantitative imaging of intracellular calcium (PMID: 34887382). In addition, Node staff published about the role of the IL-1 pathway for the control of the number of pathogenic cytosolic mycobacteria (PMID: 33952660).
- The Node was involved in 4 training courses. The ImageJ course included participants from almost all Dutch Euro-Biolmaging Nodes. A Masterclass in Fluorescence Microscopy for 20 high school students was also organized.

3

FACILITIES

8

EXTERNAL USERS

24,375

USAGE HOURS

N/A

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

10.2

STAFF INVOLVED

4

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

NETHERLANDS

WAGENINGEN IMAGING AND SPECTROSCOPY HUB (WISH) - ALM AND MOLECULAR IMAGING NODE WAGENINGEN

Node contact: Johannes Hohlbein

johannes.hohlbein@wur.nl

Website: [www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/wageningen-imaging-and-spectroscopy-hub-\(wish\)--alm-and-molecular-imaging-node-wageningen](http://www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/wageningen-imaging-and-spectroscopy-hub-(wish)--alm-and-molecular-imaging-node-wageningen)

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node provides access to light microscopy and optical spectroscopy services.
- The Node continued to run university courses for “Spectroscopy and Imaging”, “Biophotonics and Photosynthesis”, “Advanced Methods in Biochemical Research”, “Biophysical Imaging”.
- The MSC site of the Node moved much of the equipment into a single large room now dedicated to fluorescence imaging & spectroscopy.

New instruments:

- Rescan-confocal microscope, which offers improved resolution for confocal microscopy. Funding for an optical tweezer setup (Picoquant Microtime 200 + JPK Bruker optical tweezer unit) to be installed in 2022, was also obtained.

2

FACILITIES

27

EXTERNAL USERS

15,100

USAGE HOURS

5.4M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

3

STAFF INVOLVED

50*

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED
*including personal trainings

NORWAY

NORMIC OSLO - ADVANCED LIGHT MICROSCOPY NODE OSLO

Node contact: Oddmund Bakke

oddmund.bakke@ibv.uio.no

Website: www.mn.uio.no/ibv/english/research/infrastructure/facilities/life-science/imaging/normic

HIGHLIGHTS

- Node staff are heavily involved in a masters course in Methods in cell biology - teaching theory and giving 30 master students practical experience in transfection and imaging techniques.
- The Node coordinates “Bridging Nordic Microscopy Infrastructures, BNMI” funded by Nordic Research Council to support Nordic imaging courses & interactions, involving multiple Euro-Biolmaging Nodes. More info: www.BNMI.eu

New instruments:

- Nikon spinning disc SoRa system and OLYMPUS VS200 slide scanner. The facility obtained funding for a live-cell light microscope with a photo-stimulation device from Fougner Hartmann Familiefond.

1

FACILITIES

48

EXTERNAL USERS

16,030

USAGE HOURS

5M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

4

STAFF INVOLVED

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

NORWAY

NORMOLIM, NORWEGIAN MOLECULAR IMAGING INFRASTRUCTURE

Node contact: Deborah Hill
deborah.hill@ntnu.no

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/normolim.-norwegian-molecular-imaging-infrastructure

10

FACILITIES

32

EXTERNAL USERS

4,347

USAGE HOURS

6.8M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

9

STAFF INVOLVED

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- We received two major grants. First, a renewal of KG Jebsen center for Cardiac research, value 14 MNOK. Second, a 15 MNOK grant for investigation of cardiomyopathy in salmon, using both MRI and ultrasound.
- UiB:** Opened a new imaging lab for small animals, where PET/MR, Optical imaging, Ultrasound and Multiphoton imaging systems are localized in close vicinity.
- NTNU:** Infrastructure day for personalized medicine with over 120 participants.

New instrument:

- MR Solutions Powerscan 7T PET/MR

PORTUGAL

PORTUGUESE BRAIN IMAGING NETWORK (BIN)

Node contact: Miguel Castelo-Branco
mcbranco@fmed.uc.pt

Website: www.uc.pt/en/brainimaging/

4

FACILITIES

15

EXTERNAL USERS

5,200

USAGE HOURS

7M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

9

STAFF INVOLVED

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node participates in major European grants (STIPED, AIMS-2-Trials) and in 2021 finished a major grant (2.5M euros).
- The Node coordinates research activities of 5 major research Institutes in Portugal, demonstrating the ability to coordinate scientific teams and complex neuroimaging projects.
- Node staff recently published a paper on interplay between low and high-level visual mechanisms and their impact on neural plasticity from the point of view of molecular mechanisms.

New instruments:

- 2 new PET scanners for humans.

POLAND

ADVANCED LIGHT MICROSCOPY NODE

Node contact: Jędrzej Szymański
j.szymanski@nencki.edu.pl

Website: www.eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/advanced-light-microscopy-node-poland

3

FACILITIES

32

EXTERNAL USERS

12,310

USAGE HOURS

5.5M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

8

STAFF INVOLVED

1

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- 2021 was a memorable year! Poland finally became a Euro-Biolmaging member country and we became a Node.
- The vast majority of microscopy trainings for users were performed remotely. Technicians also recorded video materials for our users.

New instruments:

- The LMU at Nencki Institute purchased: a new automated super-resolution microscope for live cell imaging Zeiss Celldiscoverer 7 with Airyscan, Leica laser microdissection microscope and Nanolive high precision tomographic microscope 3D Cell Explorer.
- The facility was also connected to a HIVE data storage and analysis system.

PORTUGAL

PORTUGUESE PLATFORM OF BIOIMAGING (PPBI)

Node contact: Paula Sampaio
sampaio@i3s.up.pt

Website: www.ppbi.pt

13

FACILITIES

238

EXTERNAL USERS

117,388

USAGE HOURS

>15M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

49

STAFF INVOLVED

17

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

HIGHLIGHTS

- The Node loves to organize things and didn't let the pandemic stop them. The Node attempted hybrid training, on site, plus broadcasting for the other sites of the Node. Also they organized full online Microscopy, Tissue clearing and Image Analysis courses with high national and international participation.
- Staff from the Node were awarded 2 IGC best talks awards.
- 2021 was very busy with increasing demand from users despite the pandemic.

New instruments:

- 5 new microscopes at the IGC, IMM and CEDOC, including spinning disk and laser scanning confocals and super-resolution systems.

SWEDEN

SWEDISH NATIONAL MICROSCOPY INFRASTRUCTURE

Node contact: Hjalmar Brismar brismar@kth.se

Website: www.nmisweden.se

HIGHLIGHTS

- In 2021 NMI received major funding from the Swedish research council to upgrade equipment in Stockholm, Gothenburg and Umeå.
- CCI is part of the RltrainPlus project, (<https://rltrainplus.eu/>): bringing together research infrastructures, core facilities, business management schools and European universities to train tomorrow's RI managers.

New instruments:

- **KTH:** Zeiss lattice light sheet and 980-Airy-scan 2, ELYRA 7.
- **CCI:** CD7/LSM900 Airyscan 2, Zeiss ELYRA 7, EDX detector for the GEMINI450 system.
- **Umeå:** Cyro-EM Glacios from Thermo Fisher.

5

FACILITIES

50

EXTERNAL USERS

45,000

USAGE HOURS

19.4M

INVESTMENTS IN INSTRUMENTS

16

STAFF INVOLVED

10

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

SWEDEN

Part of the team from our Swedish NMI Node show off their Euro-BioImaging T-shirts in December 2021. Left, the team at KTH and right, Node Coordinator Hjalmar Brismar (far right), Hans Blom (middle), in a video conference with Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez (computer screen), Head of the Center for Cellular Imaging.

NORWAY

Marina and Apsana are excited to use one of the newer microscopes in their studies of micronuclei at the NorMIC Oslo imaging platform (Photo courtesy of NorMIC-Oslo).

2021 AT OUR NODES WAS...

“ We are looking forward to have the international users back in our Node post-Covid!

- Nalan Liv, CLEM Dutch Flagship Node

“ This was a great year, with a significant upgrade of our Molecular Imaging Facilities.

- Miguel Castelo-Branco, Portuguese Brain Imaging Network

“ COVID restricted access to the facility. Fortunately most image analysis activities could be managed remotely. As such we could support at least all internal users and some external users.

- Aad van der Lugt, Population Imaging Flagship Node Rotterdam

“ We were able to maintain regular operation despite the pandemic. The research carried out at the Node resulted in several high impact publications.

- Prof. János Szöllősi and Dr. György Vámosi, Cellular Imaging Hungary Node

“ An exceptionally good year in terms of publications and companies as users.

- Marc van Zandvoort, AMMI Maastricht Node

“ COVID restrictions have severely lowered the number of external but especially foreign microscope users. The temporal release of restrictions in autumn 2021 resulted in an instant increase of interested users. Thus we are optimistic that in 2022 we will 'return to normal'.

- Mark Hink, (LCAM) - Functional Imaging Flagship Node Amsterdam

“ 2021 was almost like a normal year, with high activity. Pandemic precautions did not seriously interfere with daily operations.

- Deborah Hill, NORMOLIM Node

“ 2021 was strange and more busy than ever. Our facility had to learn how to protect users and staff from COVID-19, while at the same time accommodating scientists, home due to travelling restrictions, and to image more than ever.

- Clara Prats, Danish BioImaging

“ A challenging year, but exciting at the same time, with many great new projects coming from all over the world: Europe, USA, China, Canada! Someone said: 'Difficult roads often lead to beautiful destinations.'

- Julia Fernandez Rodriguez, Swedish NMI

“ Overall, 2021 was a positive year with the restart of the activities after the peak of the pandemic period. User access increased and new instruments entered our technological imaging portfolio.

- Enzo Terreno, Danilo Porro, Antonio Esposito, Luca Menichetti, Nicola Belcari, A. Giorgetti, Marcello Mancini, Marco Salvatore, MMMI Italian Node

“ We are happy to say that in spite the COVID difficulties high level services was maintained, and new equipment was installed. In addition, new labs were established with advanced imaging methods for single molecule detection in living organisms - the MiLabs PET/SPECT/CT/OI was purchased. As well as a new clinical 3T MRI facility.

- Michal Neeman, Israel BioImaging

COMMUNITY BUILDING

FLAGSHIP EVENTS

Euro-BioImaging is extremely active in engaging with the biological and biomedical imaging communities and organizing events for the benefit of the whole community. In 2021, we organized a number of flagship events open to all imaging enthusiasts, including two Euro-BioImaging **User Forums** and the weekly **Virtual Pub**. But we didn't stop there. We also attended a number of conferences and engaged with Node staff, the wider community and industry colleagues via our **Expert Groups**. In addition, we contributed to events organized by the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board and continued to be active internationally. In these pages of the Annual Report, we present some highlights of the year.

EURO-BIOIMAGING USER FORUM

Biological and biomedical imaging technologies are crucial to cancer research. To explore this theme and to promote our Nodes' expertise in the field, we decided to organize a new virtual event for the benefit of the entire imaging community. Our first User Forum took place in June 2021 and it was so successful that we organized a second one with the same theme in October. Designed to highlight the importance of imaging to understanding and fighting cancer, these events featured keynote

presentations from prominent scientists as well as a focus on presentations from users from our Nodes. Both events attracted researchers, students, core facility staff, policy makers and industry representatives from 26 countries. We recorded the second User Forum and the talks are available on our YouTube channel. Thank you to all who participated!

VISIT OUR PLAYLIST:

UNDERSTANDING & FIGHTING CANCER

397

CUMULATIVE
PARTICIPANTS

4

KEYNOTE
SPEAKERS

9

NODES
PRESENTED

25+

COUNTRIES

220

VIEWS ON
YOUTUBE

6

EARLY CAREER
SPEAKERS

VIRTUAL PUB

In 2021, Euro-Biolmaging continued to organize the online Virtual Pub events, a free weekly lecture, open to the entire imaging community. Topics include new biological & biomedical imaging technologies, image analysis, and Node presentations. The Virtual Pub events significantly increase the visibility of our infrastructure, as is shown by the exponential growth of our Virtual Pub mailing list in 2021.

45

VIRTUAL PUBS IN 2021

2,000+

CUMULATIVE PARTICIPANTS

2,141

VIEWS ON YOUTUBE

200+

NEW CONTACTS

CORRELATED IMAGING SERIES

Every third Friday of the month, starting in July 2021, in collaboration with COMULIS (a EU-funded COST Action Project), the Virtual Pub hosted the "Correlated Imaging Series." Talks focused on correlative multi-modality imaging combining a range of different imaging techniques and the biological and biomedical applications they can address. Many of the Euro-Biolmaging Nodes specialize in correlative and multimodal imaging and the challenges and expertise required for such projects are specifically well-suited to be addressed through research infrastructure services. It is therefore important for Euro-Biolmaging to highlight this specific approach and we are glad to have the opportunity to collaborate with COMULIS. The collaboration of Euro-Biolmaging and COMULIS has been very positive for the visibility of both organisations and for correlative imaging in general. The series continues in 2022.

6

LECTURES

333

PARTICIPANTS

488

VIEWS ON YOUTUBE

80,249

CUMULATIVE VIEWS ON TWITTER

CONFERENCES

We are deeply involved in the biological and biomedical imaging communities, and gladly take part in community events as invited speakers or by organizing workshops or special sessions about the opportunities Euro-Biolmaging provides to researchers - or about life science research infrastructures as a whole. In 2021, many events continued to be virtual due to the pandemic, but some events took place in person (like EMIM in Germany) or in hybrid format (like EMBL Young Scientists' Forum in Poland).

40+

COMMUNITY OR POLICY EVENTS ATTENDED

30

POSTERS OR PRESENTATIONS

7

SPECIAL SESSIONS WITH NODES OR PARTNERS

EMIM - Silvio Aime and Giuseppe Diglio of the Euro-Biolmaging Med Hub team at EMIM in Göttingen, Germany (August 2021). We had a booth and organized a special session featuring presentations from our Nodes and the partner RI INFRAFRONTIER entitled "Euro-Biolmaging and INFRAFRONTIER: Open access to imaging technologies and animal models to support your research."

EMBO Young Scientists' Forum - Johanna Bischof of the Bio-Hub team presented Euro-Biolmaging at the EMBO Young Scientists' Forum in Warsaw, Poland (October 2021). She combined this presentation opportunity with a visit to our brand new Advanced Light Microscopy Node Poland.

The Czech-Biolmaging scientific conference - "Imaging Principles of Life 2021" was held in person in October 2021. Johanna Bischof presented the opportunities of Euro-Biolmaging to the Czech Biolmaging community, including staff from the Prague and Brno Nodes.

CELL BIO - an ASCB & EMBO Meeting - In collaboration with our partner research infrastructures EU-OPENSREEN and Instruct, we organized a Networking session for early career researchers on Training at International Research Infrastructures at the virtual Cell Bio meeting in December 2021.

INDUSTRY

The Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board (EBIB) provides a platform for Biological and Biomedical Imaging companies to communicate and collaborate with the wider Euro-Biolmaging community of academic and commercial users and cutting-edge imaging facilities with the goal of strengthening imaging research in Europe. In 2021, the EBIB has not only grown from 11 to 14 members, but has also found many ways of interacting with the imaging community remotely.

INSIGHT

Overall, 2021 offered ample visibility to the Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board and opportunities for interaction. The feedback collected during the events and in a survey conducted by the Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board Coordinator among the Euro-Biolmaging Nodes, suggests in-person workshops and personal interactions with companies on clearly defined topics and among a smaller group of speakers with similar interests are expected to provide most additional benefit and will be explored in 2022.

READ MORE:

VIRTUAL PUB SPECIAL EDITIONS

Two Special Editions of the Virtual Pub invited speakers from industry and academia for a round of flash presentations on how their research and technology relates to the themes of "Speed" and "Cold". The short and fun format brought together a wide range of presentations and listeners. The events were sponsored by the Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board with small prizes going to participants and winners of an audience vote on the best presentation.

NODES & INDUSTRY MEETING

"LIVING COLLABORATIONS"

On October 27-28, 2021, Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board in collaboration with Euro-Biolmaging organized a 1.5-day "Nodes & Industry Meeting" on the topic of "3D Imaging". It culminated in a two hour "Living collaborations" session during which 4 examples of successful collaborations between imaging facilities and companies were presented, ranging from joint training and demo activities to commercialization of technology. This was followed by a panel discussion exploring the mutual rewards and impact that these interactions bring to companies and the research community. The event provided new insights into what makes such collaborations work and was enjoyed by all participants.

INTERNSHIP PROGRAM

At the end of the year, two Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board members signed a trilateral Memorandum of Understanding with Euro-Biolmaging and the Master's programme in Biomedical Imaging (BIMA) in Turku, Finland, to offer internship places to selected participants in the programme that will be credited towards their MSc degree. In a two-year pilot phase, students will apply for an opportunity to get to know different job profiles in industry. First students are expected in Spring 2022 and if successful, the collaboration might be extended to additional MSc programme and companies in the future.

READ MORE:

TECH EXCHANGE

The Industry Board launched the Tech Exchange in March 2021 as its own 1-hour webinar series for Imaging companies to present their latest technology, products and applications. After 4 episodes in 2021, the webinar will be presented monthly in 2022.

INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

Euro-Biolmaging ERIC has many flourishing international relations with imaging infrastructures and communities around the globe, as it is a founding partner of the Global Biolmaging (GBI) network (www.globalbioimaging.org).

GLOBAL BIOIMAGING

EXCHANGE OF EXPERIENCE VI

The 6th edition of GBI's annual Exchange of Experience gathering focused on "Imaging Research Infrastructures in a time of change." Claudia Kuntner-Hannes, Medical University of Vienna, part of **Austrian Biolmaging/ CMI** (our Austrian Node) was invited to give a keynote on "The importance and potential of Correlative Imaging in today's research." The event attracted the interest of more than 170 registered participants from over 30 countries around the globe.

TRAINING

Global Biolmaging, with support from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, provides training opportunities in multiple avenues including core facility management, image data, and novel biological and biomedical imaging technologies for directors and staff of imaging infrastructures and imaging core facilities. In 2021, GBI designed an online Training Platform with multiple modules for beginners to advanced microscopists. This curated resource is free and open to all.

LEARN MORE ABOUT TRAINING OPPORTUNITIES FROM GBI:

COLLABORATION WITH AUSTRALIA

Australia is one of our historic partners, as we have collaborated with Australian imaging infrastructures for exchange of experience, job shadowing and training since 2011. Antje Keppler presented our collaboration with Australia in the presence of European and Australian funders at the RI-VIs Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures in October 2021. In the same month, we renewed our Cooperation Agreement with Microscopy Australia.

CELEBRATING 10 YEARS!

STRENGTHENING TIES WITH LATIN AMERICA

POLICY EVENT IN URUGUAY

To support the advancement of imaging in the region we organized a meeting along with partner research infrastructure Instruct ERIC to bring together the Ambassador of Finland in Argentina, researchers from the Institut Pasteur Montevideo, Academy of Finland representatives, and policy makers from Uruguay, to facilitate discussion on creating a Regional Hub in Latin America.

Visit of the Finnish Ambassador to IP Montevideo as part of a policy event organized by Euro-Biolmaging and Instruct. Photo credit: IP Montevideo (Twitter)

RI-VIS LATIN AMERICA - EUROPE SYMPOSIUM

In 2021, we followed the evolution of the Latin America Bioimaging community - a newly created network that brings together bioimaging researchers, service providers, educators and commercial technology integrators across the region - with great excitement. Together with Global Biolmaging and Latin America Biolmaging, we organized a satellite event at the RI-VIS Latin America - Europe Symposium, to share the experiences and lessons learnt on building Euro-Biolmaging to support the advancement of Latin America Bioimaging, at the political and scientific level.

QUAREP-LiMi

Euro-Biolmaging Hub and Node staff are very active in QUAREP-LiMi, a group of light microscopists dedicated to improving quality assessment and quality control in light microscopy. This grassroots community has made amazing progress over the last year. QUAREP-LiMi Working Group 1 released a protocol for monitoring illumination power and stability, which is an important step for instrument quality control. In late 2021, our Image Data Coordinator, Aastha Mathur became co-lead of QUAREP-LiMi Working Group 7 on Metadata along with Caterina Strambio De Castillia and Kenneth Ho. This working group, together with other imaging communities, worked towards establishing community-approved guidelines and tools for improving reporting and reproducibility of

microscopy metadata. These achievements, along with advancements in Next Generation File Formats and Global policies on image data sharing, were brought together in the Nature Methods "Focus" on Reporting and Reproducibility in Microscopy published in December 2021.

Image copyright: Thao Do, Allen Institute, Seattle, WA, USA

EXPERT GROUPS

Euro-Biolmaging organizes a wide range of topic-oriented Expert Groups. With these Expert Groups, our mission is to increase collaboration and connections between our Nodes and give core facility staff the opportunity to share and advance their knowledge on many relevant topics. Several of the Expert Groups are also open to the wider imaging community - including Euro-Biolmaging friends, partners, Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board members and more. Here we highlight outcomes from just a few of these groups. Visit our website to learn more: www.eurobioimaging.eu/about-us/expert-groups

TECHNOLOGY EXPERT GROUPS DEVELOP A NEW FRAMEWORK FOR EURO-BIOIMAGING TECHNOLOGY PRESENTATION

In March 2021, we formed three expert groups – for light microscopy, electron microscopy, and biomedical imaging technologies. These expert groups represent the broad spectrum of expertise available at our Nodes. Their goal was to achieve a user-oriented and flexible presentation of our technology portfolio. Through regular meetings and in-depth discussions throughout 2021 the expert groups developed a new categorization and presentation for all technologies on offer at the Euro-Biolmaging Nodes.

To ensure the new technology framework is aligned with imaging technology terminology, Euro-Biolmaging collaborated with Dr. Joelle Goulding, University of Nottingham, who leads the RMS Dictionary of Light Microscopy project. This allowed us to find harmonized spelling and terminology for the terms included in both the Euro-Biolmaging technology framework and the Light Microscopy Dictionary.

The new technology framework will be implemented in 2022 and will serve our users to get an overview of all available technologies and find the most suited one for their project.

74

MEMBERS

14

COUNTRIES

18

NODES

COMMUNICATION EXPERT GROUP EXPANDS PRESENCE ON SOCIAL MEDIA

The Communications Expert Group got started in October 2020 and met at regular intervals throughout 2021. Meetings were organized as an exchange of experience with Node and Hub representatives (and sometimes outside guests) sharing their know-how on a variety

of communication channels and tools. Topics included Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, organizing an online event, image contests, video creation, newsletters, European Researchers' Night and annual reports. An outcome of this Expert group was the creation of LinkedIn accounts at PPBI, PRIME and France-Bio-Imaging in 2021.

33

MEMBERS

11

COUNTRIES

17

FACILITIES REPRESENTED

EXPERT GROUP ON REMOTE ACCESS AND TRAINING

The Euro-Biolmaging Expert Group on Remote Access and Training has been meeting monthly since 2020 to facilitate exchange between the Euro-Biolmaging Nodes on tools and solutions for providing remote access and remote training to facility users. Arising from the activities of this Expert Group, Euro-Biolmaging organized a 1-day workshop together with partner RI, Instruct ERIC, as part of the EOSC-Life project. This Exchange of Experience workshop, on April 14th 2021, brought together 124 participants from a variety of different Research Infrastructures from the life sciences and beyond to discuss challenges and share experiences in remote access service provision and training.

Experts from five Euro-Biolmaging Nodes participated as trainers in the workshop, including with live demos of remote microscope access.

Rafael Camacho and Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez from the NMI Sweden Node provided a live demo of remote access to a microscope and shared their system for remote user training.

“The best part of the workshop for me was the shared experiences from facility managers and realizing that everyone has the same problems. Also the willingness of the participants in sharing their own creative and ingenious solutions for solving the problems mentioned.”

- Comment by a participant from the post-course survey

SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media, namely **Twitter**, continued to be an important part of our community-building strategy in 2021. We used Twitter to interact with a variety of partners, give visibility to imaging scientists and our Nodes, promote breakthroughs in imaging research, and advertise our Flagship events. We also grew our community on **LinkedIn** with the creation of LinkedIn Events pages to advertise the Euro-Biolmaging User Forums and the Correlated Imaging Series lectures in collaboration with COMULIS Cost. We increased our followers on **YouTube** in 2021 by continuing to create video content to promote imaging technologies, the Virtual Pub and the User Forum.

3,900+

FOLLOWERS

2,100+

CONNECTIONS

200

SUBSCRIBERS

900

NEW FOLLOWERS IN 2021

600

NEW CONNECTIONS IN 2021

190

NEW SUBSCRIBERS IN 2021

GOVERNANCE

OUR GOVERNANCE

Euro-BioImaging is managed by its Hub and governed by the Euro-BioImaging Board. Our governance also includes a Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), to oversee the scientific, ethical, technical and quality management of the Euro-BioImaging ERIC activities. The Panel of Nodes, representing the individual Nodes, advises the Euro-BioImaging Directorate. In addition, the Industry Board Advisory Panel interacts with the Directorate on industry-relevant aspects.

OUR MULTI-FACETED GOVERNANCE

DID YOU KNOW

Euro-BioImaging became an ERIC in December 2019. During the pandemic, we waited patiently for our “plate,” the official plaque with our name on it that is given to all European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs). On March 25th, 2022,

we received our plate at the ESFRI 20 years event in Paris, France. Today the plate is housed at the Euro-BioImaging Statutory Seat in Turku, Finland. We are so happy to have our plate at last!

From left to right: Jana Kolar, ESFRI Chair, John Eriksson, Euro-BioImaging Director General, Jean-Eric Paquet, Director General for Research and Innovation, European Commission, and Antje Keppler, Bio-Hub Director. Photo courtesy of ESFRI.

EURO-BIOIMAGING BOARD

The Euro-BioImaging Board is the principal decision-making body for the overall strategy and the policy for integrated operation and further development of Euro-BioImaging ERIC. The Board approves all strategic decisions, and oversees the performance of the Hub and Nodes with input from the Scientific Advisory Board and the Euro-BioImaging Directorate.

The Board meets at least twice a year. Prof. Benjamin Geiger and Dr. Suvi Broholm have served as Chair and Vice-Chair of the Euro-BioImaging Board since December 2019, and along with all delegates of Euro-BioImaging members, have done an excellent job ensuring that our infrastructure runs smoothly and fulfills its strategic & operational goals to date.

CHAIR

BENJAMIN GEIGER
Principal Investigator,
Weizman Institute of
Science, Israel

VICE-CHAIR

SUVI BROHOLM
Scientific Advisor, Academy
of Finland

A CHANGING OF THE GUARDS

As our research infrastructure grows and matures, our leadership will inevitably change. After dedicated service since 2019, Suvi Broholm announced she would step down from her role as Vice-Chair of the Euro-BioImaging Board. We are very grateful for her contribution. We are also thankful that Benny Geiger will take on another mandate as Euro-BioImaging Board Chair.

He has been our Chair since 2015. His extraordinary commitment to Euro-Bio-Imaging has contributed to the stability of our infrastructure and ensured the seamless transition from preparatory phase to interim phase to operations. We are very pleased to have him with us for another mandate period.

WELCOME TO OUR NEW BOARD VICE-CHAIR

In May 2022, Jan Buriánek was appointed as the Vice-Chair of the Euro-BioImaging ERIC Board. Since 2012, Jan Buriánek has been at the Czech Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, Unit of Research Infrastructures. He was named Head of Unit of Research Infrastructures between 2019-2020. He represents his country in numerous research organizations and international research infrastructures. We welcome Jan Buriánek in his new role and are very happy to have him on board!

JAN BURIÁNEK
Research Infrastructures
Unit, Czech Ministry of
Education, Youth and
Sports

SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD

The Euro-BioImaging Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) oversees the quality of Euro-BioImaging activities at the coordinating Hub and the Nodes, including the evaluation of new Nodes. This group of independent, highly-qualified, internationally recognized scientific, ethical and technical experts, was constituted in July 2020, and immediately undertook the major task of evaluating the Expressions of Interest of the 2020 Call for Nodes. In 2021, the Scientific Advisory Board was again mobilized to assess Node candidates to conclude the process begun in 2020. As a result, over the course of 2020-2021, 11 new Nodes and 5 Node upgrades were added to Euro-BioImaging, a nearly 50 percent increase with regards to the 2019 status. We want to thank the Scientific Advisory Board for their important contribution to scaling the Euro-BioImaging infrastructure. Under their watch, our infrastructure has grown significantly, while assuring the highest standards of service for Euro-BioImaging users. In 2022, the Scientific Advisory Board will again be mobilized to evaluate the Euro-BioImaging ERIC (Hub and Node) activities. With their vigilance, we will keep our infrastructure cutting-edge and build the strong foundations for the future of imaging.

2020-2021 SAB MEMBERS

- **CAROLYN ANDERSON**, University of Missouri, USA
- **ZAVER BHUJWALLA**, Johns Hopkins Medicine, USA
- **TENG-LEONG CHEW**, HHMI Janelia, USA
- **SCOTT FRASER**, University of Southern California, USA
- **GRAHAM GALLOWAY**, University of Queensland, Australia
- **KATHARINA GAUS***, EMBL Australia Node/UNSW, Australia
- **WOJTEK JAMES GOSCINSKI**, Monash University, Australia
- **PHILIP HOCKBERGER**, Northwestern University, USA
- **HEDVIG HRICAK**, Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, USA
- **JUDY ILLES**, University of British Columbia, Canada
- **ALISON NORTH**, Rockefeller University, USA
- **SHUICHI ONAMI**, RIKEN Center for Biosystems Dynamics Research, Japan
- **IAN SMITH**, Monash University, Australia

** Katharina Gaus passed away in March 2021. Her presence and contributions are greatly missed by the community.*

CHAIR

IAN SMITH
Vice-Provost, Office
of the Vice-Provost
(Research and Research
Infrastructure), Monash
University

CO-CHAIR

PHILIP HOCKBERGER
Associate Professor of
physiology, Feinberg
School of Medicine (FSM),
Northwestern University

PANEL OF NODES

The Euro-BioImaging Panel of Nodes is composed of the official representatives of the Euro-BioImaging Nodes. It meets regularly and its mission is to advise the Euro-BioImaging Directorate with regards to Euro-BioImaging Node activities. In 2021, the Panel of Nodes elected its chairs and began to define its operations, setting up for example, monthly meetings between Panel chairs and the Euro-BioImaging Directorate.

The Panel of Nodes is crucial for Euro-BioImaging as it not only gives advice as regards the quality and impact of the Nodes' user access and services and their support and coordination by the Hub. It also advises the Directorate in relation to testing new imaging technologies, image data management, and on major trends, future technical directions and their applications in research.

“ *The Panel of Nodes has enormous potential – it is a group of experts representing Europe’s most renowned imaging facilities. As chairs of the Euro-BioImaging Panel of Nodes, our most important missions are:*

- *To improve the feeling of being one family of Nodes, each Node being equally important and relevant - “One for all, all for one.”*
- *To stimulate exchange of knowledge and experience between Nodes.*
- *To advance the training and professional development of Node staff.*

- *To stimulate usage of the Nodes by international and national users through optimizing service provision.*
- *To foster collaboration with the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board.*
- *To propose projects and tasks that bring us together to work for the benefit of the imaging community at large.*

Together we can do so much for the benefit of imaging.

- Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez & Marc van Zandvoort

EURO-BIOIMAGING DIRECTORATE

The Euro-BioImaging Directorate is the executive body of Euro-BioImaging ERIC. It is composed of the Director General, who is the legal representative of the Euro-BioImaging ERIC, the Section Director of the Bio-Hub and the Section Director of the Med-Hub. Together they prepare and implement Euro-BioImaging ERIC tasks, as well as represent and promote the research infrastructure at the national and international level.

or Torino, Italy (Med-Hub) as part of our unique, tripartite structure.

In 2021, our new Med-Hub Director, Linda Chaabane, was recruited. Her appointment was approved by the Euro-BioImaging Board in early 2022. The transitional phase between Interim Directorate and Directorate is now complete!

In addition, each of the Directors has a specific management role with regards to the supporting teams located in Turku, Finland (Statutory Seat), EMBL Heidelberg (Bio-Hub)

EURO-BIOIMAGING INDUSTRY BOARD ADVISORY PANEL

Close collaboration between Euro-BioImaging ERIC and Industry is key to the success of the infrastructure, to continuously include the latest technology developments and make them accessible to the European research community, including industrial researchers.

Euro-BioImaging also established an Advisory Panel of EBIB representatives to provide advice to the Euro-BioImaging Directorate on Industry-relevant needs and initiatives that should be addressed by Euro-BioImaging.

Throughout its preparatory phases, Euro-BioImaging was widely supported by the imaging industry united in the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board (EBIB), which was set up in 2014. At the formal start of the ERIC,

CHAIR

MARC VAN ZANDVOORT

Advanced Microscopy and Multimodal Imaging (AMMI) Node – Maastricht

CO-CHAIR

JULIA FERNANDEZ-RODRIGUEZ

Swedish National Microscopy Infrastructure Node

MARTIN TEWINKEL
Chair of Euro-BioImaging Industry Board & EBIB Advisory Panel

CLAUDIA PFANDER
Euro-BioImaging Industry Board Coordinator

HERBERT SCHADEN
Vice Chair of Euro-BioImaging Industry Board & EBIB Advisory Panel

FINANCIAL INFORMATION

INCOME & EXPENSES

Euro-BioImaging ERIC is financed by the annual membership contributions from the ERIC members. 'Income membership contributions 2021' shows the total membership contributions for the financial period (01.01.2021-31.12.2021). Euro-BioImaging Hub is formed by the Statutory seat, the Bio-Hub and the Med-Hub. Euro-BioImaging Statutory Seat collects the annual membership contributions of Euro-BioImaging ERIC. 'Budget transfer' indicates the agreed membership contribution budget shares transferred from the Euro-BioImaging

Statutory seat to the Bio-Hub and Med-Hub sections, respectively. Income at each Hub section are indicated separately. 'Expenses' show the actual realized expenses by cost category during the financial period at each Euro-BioImaging Hub Section. The report includes reserve funds that carry-over funds available after the expenses of the financial period. This funding reserve will be warranted especially for liquidity required to buffer reimbursement delays incurred at the onset of funded Horizon Europe projects.

INCOME (€)	STATUTORY SEAT	BIO-HUB	MED-HUB	THROUGH THE ERIC
Membership Contributions 2021	1,431,876.72			1,431,876.72
Budget Transfer (Bio-Hub)	- 572,175.00	572,175.00		
Budget Transfer (Med-Hub)	- 241,480.00		241,480.00	
Income, by Hub section	618,221.72	572,175.00	241,480.00	1,431,876.72

EXPENSES (€)	STATUTORY SEAT	BIO-HUB	MED-HUB	THROUGH THE ERIC
Human resources	137,813.42	392,292.95	25,259.00	555,365.37
External services (human resources*)	113,168.67			113,168.67
Travel		857.57		857.57
Services		6,509.08		6,509.08
Financial and administration expenses	5,107.27			5,107.27
Other expenses	51,864.37	6,473.68		58,338.05
Total expenses	307,953.73	406,133.28	25,259.00	739,346.01

* Human resource expenses incurred at the University of Turku and were billed to the Euro-BioImaging ERIC Statutory Seat

FUNDS (RESERVE, €)	STATUTORY SEAT	BIO-HUB	MED-HUB	THROUGH THE ERIC
Jan 1 - Dec 31, 2021	310,267.99	166,041.72	216,221.00	692,530.71
Oct 29, 2019 - Dec 31, 2020*	765,474.81	407,350.97	7,178.72	1,180,004.50
Total	1,075,742.80	573,392.69	223,399.72	1,872,535.21

* Statutory seat allocation includes 25051,39 of Med-Hub unspent funds of 2019

Costs booked on additional external funding sources at each Euro-BioImaging Hub section were as indicated.

COSTS BOOKED ON ADDITIONAL EXTERNAL FUNDING SOURCES DURING 2021 (€)	STATUTORY SEAT	BIO-HUB	MED-HUB
EOSC Life*		108,482.41	
Host premium contribution: Euro-BioImaging ERIC HQ - launching of operations**	441,512.00		
In-kind		0.5 FTE (EMBL)	1.1 FTE (UNITO), INFRASTRUCTURE COSTS (UNITO), INTERIM DIRECTOR ACTIVITIES

* Costs incurred in 2021

** For the period of 2019-2021

Euro-BioImaging Hub team Meeting, April 25-27, 2022 - Heidelberg, Germany.

The Euro-BioImaging Hub team met in person for the first time since ERIC status was obtained in April 2022. It was a real pleasure to work together in a lovely setting after two years of Zoom meetings! Front row (left to right): Arina Rybina, Marianna Childress-Poli, Rakesh Mahato, Alessandra Viale, Linda Chaabane, Antje Keppler, Aastha Mathur, Johanna Bischof, Solveig Eriksson. Back row (left to right): Ilari Pulli, Camilo Guzmán, John Eriksson, Claudia Pfander, Pasi Kankaanpää, Bugra Oezdemir, Susanne Vainio, Giuseppe Digilio. (Milad Kakouli missing from picture.)

THIS ANNUAL REPORT IS A PUBLICATION OF EURO-BIOIMAGING

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Front Cover: Plant Imaging Photo courtesy of Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node - Prague.

Back cover: The image is a whole adult female zebrafish (mitfa:HRAS-GFP) cleared and imaged with OPT (optical projection tomography); viscerae 3D reconstructed in red and tumor mass in green/blue. Sample by Vicky Alvarado and Donald Fowler, image by Alex Lopes and Gaby G Martins (Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciencia /PPBI).

Many thanks to all of our friends at the Nodes and beyond who contributed time, texts, images and more to this document!

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